

Denouncing Terrorism in the West:

English Publications of Anti-terrorism Fatwa's as Western
Islamic Discourse with an analysis of the 'Open Letter to
Baghdadi'

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Introduction

With the rise of Islamism in the 20th century and the later emergence of Jihadi-Salafi¹ groups performing attacks inside and outside Muslim lands, the majority of institutional and famous Muslim scholars have rejected their methods and claims of it being a legitimate Jihad as proscribed by the Sharia.² When Western forces colonized the majority of Muslim lands in the 19th and early 20th century, many resistance movements (e.g. Mahdi movement in Sudan) were deemed legitimate in their claim of Jihad.³ Later conflicts, as the establishment of Israel, the Russian invasion of Afghanistan, and the American invasion of Iraq, were all seen as attacks on Muslim lands and so fighting in defense of those lands was considered by resistance fighters to be a legitimate cause for Jihad.⁴ But many Jihadist groups applied tactics and targets that scholars have deemed as unlawful according to Sharia law. The increased use of bombs and Muslim victims and noncombatant non-Muslim victims, many notable Muslim scholars declared public statements and fatwa's against the Jihadi groups' methods and claims. In our analysis we will discuss the rise of Islamism and its violent offshoots, and the counter responses given by Islamic scholars through fatwa's and letter-declarations. Our specific focus will be on the "Letter to Baghdadi", a letter written against the claims and acts of Abu Bakr al-Baghdadi, the current leader of the self-declared caliphate of the Islamic State

¹ For a discussion on these terms, see: Ahmad Moussalli, "Wahhabism, Salafism and Islamism: Who is the enemy?" *Conflicts forum*, may 4, 2016, accessed juli 6, 2016, <http://www.conflictsforum.org/2009/wahhabism-salafism-and-islamism/>.

² For an overview, see: Charles Kurzman, *Islamic Statements Against Terrorism*, accessed on 20-05-2016, <http://kurzman.unc.edu/islamic-statements-against-terrorism/>.

³ Malise Ruthven, *Islam in the World* (New York: Oxford University Press, 2006), 290-296. Amira K. Bennison, *Jihad and Its Interpretations in Pre-Colonial Morocco: State-society relations during the French conquest of Algeria* (London: Routledge Curzon, 2002), 42-157. John Obert Voll, 'Foundations for Renewal and Reform: Islamic Movements in the Eighteenth and Nineteenth Centuries', in *The Oxford History of Islam*, ed. John L. Esposito (New York: Oxford University Press, 1999), 516-545.

⁴ Malise Ruthven, *ibid*, 390-398, 401-405.

in Iraq and Syria (ISIS)⁵, and his adherents. The letter is one of the latest responses to Jihadi-Salafism, and is published simultaneously in Arabic and English.⁶ The synchronized release of the text in these two languages shows the two audiences in mind: a specific Arabic-Islamic one, and a global (multi-faith) one. This deliberate release in English shows the awareness this Letter needed to be available in this main globalistic language of the 21st century. An important motive for this would be because the majority of Muslims worldwide do not understand Arabic⁷, but also to provide an answer for rising Islamophobia in the West due to global terrorism.⁸ The Letter has therefore become as much, or even more so, part of Western

⁵ There are multiple titles and abbreviations used for ISIS, which is the abbreviation used in this paper. After its caliphate-declaration, ISIS dropped the reference to Iraq and Syria and simply called themselves ‘Islamic State (*al-Dawla al-Islamiyya*)’. Other abbreviations such as ISIL (Islamic State in Iraq and Levant) was mostly used by American policy officials, the Arabic DAISH (*al-Dawla al-Islamiyya fi al-‘Iraq wa al-Sham*) is generally mockingly pronounced as *Da’ish*, Arabic for ‘crusher’, and is being used more and more by non-Arabic speaking officials in the west as a way to show they don’t acknowledge ISIS as representing Islam. Faisal Irshaid, “Isis, Isil, IS or Daesh? One group, many names”, *BBC* (BBC News), december 2, 2015, <http://www.bbc.com/news/world-middle-east-27994277>.

⁶ *Open Letter To Dr. Ibrahim Awwad Al-Badri, alias ‘Abu Bakr Al-Baghdadi’, and to the fighters and followers of the self-declared ‘Islamic State’*, 2014, accessed may 22, 2016, <http://www.lettertobaghdadi.com/>. The first language of the website is also English, to have the website in Arabic is an option one can activate separately. Released in September 2014, it has been translated into several other languages as well by (mostly unaffiliated) volunteers, which are made available on the same website. Interestingly enough, it was translated into German, Spanish, and Dutch in the first months after its release, languages which are spoken in non-Muslim majority countries, before it was translated into Muslim-majority languages as Turkish and Persian. This shows the Letter was seemingly welcomed by Muslim minorities both as a reply against Islamophobia in these non-Muslim majority societies, and as a source text for Western-Islamic anti-extremism discourse among Muslim minorities in these countries, which provided a need to translate it in a short timespan. As there is already many mainstream-orthodox Islamic literature against terrorism available in Turkish and Persian, and, as languages of Muslim-majority countries, are not confronted with Islamophobia in a daily manner, the translations are more due to general interest instead of need as with Muslim minorities.

⁷ Saleh Bader Almansour, ‘On “Non-Arabic Speaking” Muslims’, *Griffith Working Papers in Pragmatics and Intercultural Communication* 3, no. 1 (2010), 39-49. English is probably also the source-language for the other translations of the Letter as the German, Dutch and Spanish translations were uploaded within four to ten weeks after the publication of the original Letter, which is a short time span to translate a thirty plus page technical Arabic text. After reviewing the Dutch, German and Spanish translations, it is clear they used the English as its main source as they placed the exact same Arabic transliterated terms with the translation of these terms, as is done in the official English translation. See for example their translations at: 1. Legal theory (*usul al-fiqh*), 5. Practical jurisprudence (*fiqh al-waq’i*), 10. *Jizya* (poll tax), and 16. *Hudud* (punishments).

⁸ On the relation between Islamophobia and global terrorism, see: Muhammad Safeer Awan, ‘Global Terror and the Rise of Xenophobia/Islamophobia: An Analysis of American Cultural Production since September 11’, *Islamic Studies* Vol. 49, no. No. 4 (2010). Gallup, ‘Islamophobia: Understanding Anti-Muslim Sentiment in the West’, April 29, 2016, accessed 23-5-2016, <http://www.gallup.com/poll/157082/islamophobia-understanding->

Islamic discourse compared to its importance in Arabic Islamic discourse. To understand the background to what the Letter responds too, we will first review the rise of Islamism at the beginning of the 20th century and the extremist offshoots it produced.⁹

Rise of Islamism in the 20th century

During the slow decline of power of the Ottoman Empire, epitomized in the French invasion of Egypt in 1798 by Napoleon¹⁰, the Ottoman sultan implemented several major reforms to its political and judicial systems beginning in 1839, known as the Tanzimat (lit. Reorganization). In these reforms European penal and financial laws were adopted, the introduction of liberal citizenship, which made Muslims and non-Muslims equal before the law, and parliamentary councils which culminated in the adoption of a constitution in 1876. These reforms were deemed as acceptable by the main Muslim scholars of the empire, as long as the newly introduced laws and systems conformed to the principles and boundaries of the Sharia. Other scholars rejected these reforms as they deemed both the Sharia principles and its methods of governance as equally fixed and determined by the Islamic tradition.¹¹

anti-muslim-sentiment-west.aspx. Krista McQueeney, 'Disrupting Islamophobia: Teaching the Social Construction of Terrorism in the Mass Media', *International Journal of Teaching and Learning in Higher Education* 26, no. 2 (2015): 297–309.

⁹ See Appendix II for a timeline.

¹⁰ Jackson Sigler, 'Engaging the Middle East: Napoleon's Invasion of Egypt', *History: Reviews of New Books* 38, no. 2 (January 18, 2010): 40–44.

¹¹ On the Tanzimat, see: Roderic Davison, *Reform in the Ottoman Empire 1856-1876* (New Jersey: Princeton University Press, 1963); Nurullah Ardiç, 'Islam and the Politics of Secularism: The Abolition of the Caliphate (1908-1924)' (Dissertation University of California, n.p., 2009), 68 – 120. Avi Rubin, 'Ottoman Modernity: The *Nizamiye* courts in the late nineteenth century' (Dissertation Harvard University, n.p., 2006), 25-125, 173-227. Mustafa Koçak, 'Islam and National Law in Turkey', in *Sharia Incorporated: A comparative overview of the legal systems of twelve muslim countries in past and present*, ed. Jan Michiel Otto (Leiden: Leiden University Press, 2010), 233-239. Ahmed Akgündüz, *Islamic Public Law (Documents on Practice from the Ottoman Archives)* (Istanbul: IUR Press, 2011), 213-287.

The Tanzimat reforms could not stop the rise of nationalism among the empire's non-Turkish subjects, and this disunity, together with European colonization and World War I, broke up the empire, ending in the abolition of the Ottoman Caliphate in 1924. At the end of the 19th century several Ottoman provinces, as Egypt and Tunisia, had become protectorate states of the British and French. Other states, as Saudi-Arabia, were formed through British backed rebellions against Ottoman rule, but the majority of states through European partitioning of the empire after World War I.¹² Although many non-Turkish Muslims were discontent with Ottoman rule, it was not their desire to abolish the Caliphate, and certainly not to be ruled by the European powers. As a response to this decline of Ottoman rule and the rise of European power, new Islamic identities were sought that could unite Muslims sociopolitically and at the same time cope with the major transformations of Muslim societies. This transnational movement was called Pan-Islamism. Its ideology was also adopted by sultan Abdulhamid II (d. 1918) wherein his title as Caliph, as opposed to being just the Ottoman sultan, was emphasized as a central leader of all Muslims to ward off the calls to nationalism and rebellion. But through his reversal of his predecessors' reforms and increasing authoritarian rule he was deposed.¹³ The overall discontent with Ottoman rule remained and was used by the European powers to incite rebellions and acceptance of colonial rule.

Important Muslim intellectuals such as Sayyid Jamal al-Din al-Afghani (d. 1897), the grandmufti of Egypt, Muhammad Abduh (d. 1905), and philosopher and ideologue of

¹² Ira M. Lapidus, *A History of Islamic Societies*, 2nd ed. (Cambridge: Cambridge University Press, 2002), 489-493.

¹³ William Shepard, *Introducing Islam* (London: Taylor & Francis, 2009), 218-220. Albert Hourani, *Arabic Thought in the Liberal Age, 1798-1939* (New York: Cambridge University Press, 1983), 106-107. Sir Thomas W. Arnold, *The Caliphate* (Oxford: Oxford University Press, 1999), 173 – 180.

Pakistan, Muhammad Iqbal (d. 1938), called for both reform of Islam and for Muslim independence whereby Islam was conceived as the Enlightenment religion par excellence.¹⁴ They argued that through adopting Western education and ways of governance, Muslims could regain the power of independence, but only by also remaining faithful to Islam, which meant that Western education and governance were viewed and expressed through Islamic discourse. In this way, modernity was going to be Islamicized and Islam modernized. They called for a return to the openness of early Islam wherein they viewed free interpretation (*ijtihad*) as the main cause behind the golden age of medieval Islam in terms of knowledge, science, and civilization. This call for a return of the Islam of the earliest generation of Muslims, the *Salaf al-Salih* (the righteous predecessors, from which the term Salafi is derived), was a very different call compared to that of the Wahhabi movement that founded Saudi-Arabia. The reformist Salafis called towards early Islam as a way to regain the dynamics of an intellectual civilization, the Wahhabi Salafis called towards early Islam to regain the purity of the early community free from any innovation.¹⁵

After the abolition of the Ottoman Caliphate, Islamist intellectuals looked for a new Caliph, but the majority of participants of the first World Islamic Congress in Mecca in 1926, representing different Muslim states and peoples, found no consensus on a specific leader.¹⁶ Not long after, one of the first Islamist organization was founded by Hassan al-Banna (d. 1949), the Egyptian Muslim Brotherhood (*Ikhwan al-Muslimin*) in 1928, which applied

¹⁴ Hourani, *ibid*, 103-160. Ruthven, *ibid*, 323-327.

¹⁵ Jacques Waardenburg, *Islam: Historical, Social and Political Perspectives* (Berlin: Walter de Gruyter, 2002), 287- 294. Moussalli, *Ibid*, 11-12. Mohammed Bin Ali, "The Islamic Doctrine of Al-Wala' wal Bara' (Loyalty and Disavowal) in Modern Salafism", (n.p.: University of Exeter, 2012), 42–66, <https://ore.exeter.ac.uk/repository/handle/10871/9181>.

¹⁶ Martin Seth Kramer, *Islam assembled: The Advent of the Muslim Congresses* (New York: Columbia University Press, 1986), 106–122.

educational programs and social services as a way to reform society into its ideological vision. Another important Islamist organization was founded in India in 1941, the Jama'at-I Islami, by Abul 'Ala Mawdudi (d. 1979).¹⁷ Both al-Banna and Mawdudi were not formally trained in the classical Islamic sciences. Apart from a general religious upbringing and education, and participation in religious orders and organizations, al-Banna was trained as a watchmaker and Mawdudi a journalist. Their occupations were typical of an important aspect shared among the majority of Islamist leaders in the 20th and 21st century in that they mostly consisted of doctors and engineers, trained in secular colleges.¹⁸

The Muslim Brotherhood expanded rapidly, especially after the Second World War, into other Arab nations through official affiliations or as inspiration for new Islamist groups.¹⁹ Mawdudi's Jama'at never gained political power in Pakistan, but did push the state ideology away from secularism by influencing its adoption of Islamic inspired laws and the official excommunication of the Ahmadiya sect.²⁰ Mawdudi's main importance was through his writings which were translated into many languages, and influenced later Islamist ideologues as Sayyid Qutb (d. 1966) and Ayatollah Khomeini (d. 1989).²¹

¹⁷ Ruthven, *Ibid.*, 307–311, 330–334.

¹⁸ Mawdudi had studied under several Deobandi scholars and attained classical qualifications (*ijazat*), but his approach to the classical sources and tradition has always been deemed anti-classical and simplistic. Seyyed Vali Reza Nasr, *Mawdudi and the making of Islamic revivalism* (New York: Oxford University Press, 1996), 14-18. Are Knudsen, 'Crescent and Sword: The Hamas Enigma', *Third World Quarterly* 26, no. 8 (1 January 2005): 1377. Devin R. Springer, James L. Regens, and David N. Edger, *Islamic radicalism and global jihad* (United States: Georgetown University Press, 2009), 28.

¹⁹ Ruthven, *Ibid.*, 318–322.

²⁰ Tayyab Mahmud, "Freedom of Religion & Religious Minorities in Pakistan: A Study of Judicial Practice", *Fordham Int'l L.J.* 19, no. 1 (1995), 40-100.

²¹ Asyraf Hj. A. B. Rahman and Nooraihan Ali, "The Influence of Al-Mawdudi and The Jama'at Al Islami Movement On Sayyid Qutb Writings", *World Journal of Islamic History and Civilization* 2, no. 4 (2012). Simon A. Wood, "Rethinking Fundamentalism, Ruhollah Khomeini, Mawlana Mawdudi, and the Fundamentalist

In his and al-Banna's writing, Islam is presented as a 'total scheme of life' which 'regulates every aspect of life', and is moved beyond the ritualistic-ethical worldview of classical Islam which approached politics in a pragmatic fashion. In Islamism, politics becomes just as essential for salvation as rituals, applying Marxist concepts whereby political liberation and soteriological liberation are collapsed into one another. In this vision a person is only truly free when he is ruled by God (i.e. Sharia) and not by men (i.e. lawmaking through democracy).²² In classical Islam, Islamic law existed together with the decrees and political organization of the ruler, whereby the former was a vast collective of diverse opinions, promulgated through judges, and regulated issues as family law (e.g. inheritance, divorce, custody), commerce, and penal law. The political decrees (e.g. taxes, land distribution, special penal law, war-and treaty declarations) were promulgated by the ruler and his viziers, and enforced through civil servants and the military. Islamic law, in all its dynamics, was enforced through the judiciary, but only provided ethical principles for governance thereby maintaining a separation of powers.²³ In Islamist thought this separation disappears as the power of lawmaking is taken away from classical schools of thought and the judges, and given to a parliament or council which codifies and determines Islamic law or Sharia-conform governance. In this way the state becomes both the creator and enforcer of its own version of Islam which it imposes on society, instead of being a facilitator of the

Model", *JCRT* 11, no. 2 (2011). Vanessa Martin, *Creating an Islamic state: Khomeini and the making of a new Iran* (United Kingdom: I. B.Tauris & Company, 2003), 129–146.

²² Ruthven, *Ibid*, 328-330, 313-315. Seyyed Nasr, *Ibid*, 80-96.

²³ Wael B. Hallaq, *The impossible state: Islam, politics, and modernity's moral predicament* (United States: Columbia University Press, 2012), 44–55. For an extensive account on politics and classical Islam, see: Ann K. S. Lambton, *State and government in Mediaeval Islam: An introduction to the study of Islamic political theory - the jurists* (New York: School of Oriental & African Studies, 1981).

dominant schools of thought within society as it was in classical Islam.²⁴ One consequence of this politicized Islam is that any form of Islam that differs from the state version can be seen as a threat to the state itself.²⁵ With the collapse of the traditional forms of governance, the partial democratization and secularization of Muslim society, and the Western (re-)arrangements of the post-colonial Muslim states (e.g. borders and rulers), Islam was presented as the solution to acquire true justice, independence, self-identity, and governance that would trump any non-Islamic counterpart. In this ideological construction, Islam is idealized and absolutized to serve both as a countermovement (e.g. against Western political and cultural hegemony, communism, secularism) and as an adoptive scheme (e.g. to Islamicize democracy, socialism, constitutionalism, banking, modern law).²⁶ This counter responsive element explains the different ways Islamist thought developed in different countries as it responded to different social histories, presents, and needs. But one common feature is shared by all Islamist groups: that the Sharia governs all areas of law, politics, and public morality.²⁷ What is meant by Sharia governance covers a wide spectrum, from Islamist democratic constitutionalism (e.g. Egypt)²⁸ to authoritarian monarchy (e.g. Saudi-Arabia)²⁹ to

²⁴ Seyyed Nasr, *Ibid*, 57. Bassam Tibi, *Islamism and Islam* (New Haven: Yale University Press, 2012), 1, 15, 24–25. Abdelilah Belkeziz, *The state in contemporary Islamic thought: A historical survey of the Major Muslim political thinkers of the modern era* (United Kingdom: I. B.Tauris & Company, 2009), 119–218. Moussalli, *Ibid*, 23-29.

²⁵ Tibi, *Ibid*, 231-234.

²⁶ As captured in the famous Muslim Brotherhood slogan “The solution is Islam (*al-Hall huwa al-Islam*)”. Tibi, *Ibid*, 37.

²⁷ Graham E. Fuller, “The Spectrum of Islamic Politics”, in *Islamism: Contested perspectives on political Islam*, edited by Richard C. Martin and Abbas Barzegar (United States: Stanford University Press, 2009), 51–56.

²⁸ Maurits Berger and Nadia Sonneveld, “Sharia and national law in Egypt”, in *Sharia incorporated: A comparative overview of the legal systems of Twelve Muslim countries in past and present*, edited by Jan Michiel Otto (Leiden: Leiden University Press, 2010), 51–88. Annette Ranko, *The Muslim brotherhood and its quest for hegemony in Egypt: State-discourse and Islamist counter-discourse* (Germany: Springer VS, 2014), 43–192.

Viliyat-i Faqih (“Rule of the Jurist”, Iran).³⁰ Many Muslim countries, after gaining their independence, lost their ruling families and monarchs through military coups (e.g. Egypt, Iraq, Syria, Libya), whereby the military regimes applied secular or socialist pan-Arabism as their ideology with minimal references to Islam.³¹

In Egypt, the Muslim Brotherhood was banned several times, especially after an assassination attempt on the president in 1954, which led to mass arrests of Muslim Brotherhood members.³² One of these prisoners was Sayyid Qutb, a literature critic, whose harsh treatment in prison resulted in what is deemed the most influential Islamist literature on extremism thought, which included several books on Sharia governance and an extensive commentary on the Qur’an. In these works, Qutb declared any society not governed by the Sharia to be equal to a polytheistic pre-Islamic society (*jahili*) which must be revolted against just as the Prophet Muhammad fought against the polytheists in his time. This Islamist-extremist ideology, labelled after him as Qutbism but is generally termed Jihadi-Salafism or Radical Islamism, mixed reformist Salafism with Marxism (into a liberation theology) and Wahhabism (which labels everything non-Islamic as polytheism (*Shirk*)).³³ Qutb was executed, but his works radicalized other imprisoned Muslim Brotherhood members and who eventually formed the *al-Jama’ a al-Islamiyya*, a Jihadist group which assassinated President

²⁹ Esther van Eijk, “Sharia and national law in Saudi Arabia”, in *Sharia incorporated: A comparative overview of the legal systems of Twelve Muslim countries in past and present*, edited by Jan Michiel Otto (Leiden: Amsterdam University Press, 2010), 139–180.

³⁰ Belkeziz, *Ibid*, 219-240. Vanessa Martin, *Ibid*, 147-173.

³¹ Ranko, *Ibid*, 52.

³² *Ibid*, 64-74.

³³ Springer, Regens, and Edger, *Ibid*, 50-54. Tibi, *Ibid*, 44, 145-146. Hassan Hassan, “The Sectarianism of the Islamic state: Ideological roots and political context”, 2016, accessed juli 6, 2016, <http://carnegieendowment.org/2016/06/13/sectarianism-of-islamic-state-ideological-roots-and-political-context/j1iy>. Moussalli, *Ibid*, 11-23.

Anwar Sadat in 1981.³⁴ Sadat had tried to reconcile with the Brotherhood a decade earlier, and had amended the constitution in 1972 to state that “the principles of the Islamic Sharia are a principal source of legislation.” A similar Islamist constitutional element was also adopted by Syria to appease its local Islamist groups. But in the case of Egypt, the Brotherhood criticized Saddat severely for his peace treaty with Israel, which led him to suppress and arrest its members. Al-Azhar University in Cairo, the main Sunni authority in the world, had supported the secular regimes and was very critical of the Muslim Brotherhood (although more and more Brotherhood scholars such as Yusuf al-Qaradawi were trained at al-Azhar), responding to its Islamist and Jihadist writings through the publication of their own books and fatwa’s.³⁵

After the Arab defeat in the 1967 Six-Day war with Israel, Islamist discourse increasingly influenced public piety, visible in the rise of religious associations and veiled women, as many experienced the defeat as caused through a lack of Islamic practice in public and private life.³⁶ Also the success of the 1979 revolution in Iran encouraged Islamist aspirations. Ayatollah Khomeini’s *Viliyat-i Faqih* is one of the only Islamist schemes which was constructed and applied by classically trained scholars, politicizing the already existing hierarchy in Iran between laity and clergy. Other forms of Islamism in general want to usurp existing hierarchies and replace them with lay authorities. During the 1970’s and 80’s, Lebanon was plagued by both a civil (between Christians, Druze and Muslims) and an international war (Israel attacks against Lebanese-based PLO), which led to creation of the

³⁴ Ranko, *Ibid*, 110-113.

³⁵ Johannes J. G Jansen, *The neglected duty: The creed of Sadat’s assassins and the resurgence of Islamic Militance in the middle east* (United States: Macmillan USA, 1986), 35-62. Rachel Scott, “An ‘official’ Islamic response to the Egyptian al-jihad movement”, *Journal of Political Ideologies* 8, no. 1 (februari 2003), doi:10.1080/13569310306083.

³⁶ Tibi, *Ibid*, 112-113, 225.

Shia Islamist group Hezbollah and the Islamic Jihad Organization. The latter being one of the first Islamist-Jihadist groups to apply suicide bombings, focused mainly on embassies and American and French army barracks and troops.³⁷ The First Intifada in Palestine in 1987 resulted in the creation of a new Muslim Brotherhood affiliate, Hamas.³⁸ In Algeria during the 1990s, Islamists participated in the elections, leading to a military intervention to stop the elections. This started a civil war between Islamist-Jihadist groups and the government, causing almost a 100,000 casualties.³⁹ In Afghanistan in 1978, a communist party seized power which caused a civil war with Muslims fighters (the *Mujahideen*), who were supported by the United States, which led to an invasion by the Soviet Union.⁴⁰ It was this conflict that attracted many non-Afghan Jihadists who would become important leaders of later Jihadist groups, including Osama bin Laden (d. 2011) who took over leadership of al-Qaeda after the death of its main founder Abdullah Yusuf Azzam (d. 1989).⁴¹ After the Soviet retreat in 1989, the Taliban were formed from the Mujahideen which slowly took over Afghanistan and in 1996 formed a government, implanting a harsh version of Sharia law and ruling through a non-elected council of Taliban leaders and tribal lords. This makes the Taliban neo-traditionalist, rather than Islamist, as they wanted to return to tribal pre-statehood means of governance.⁴²

³⁷ Ruthven, *Ibid*, 414-417.

³⁸ Knudsen, *Ibid*.

³⁹ Ruthven, *Ibid*, 370-373.

⁴⁰ Ruthven, *Ibid*, 396-409.

⁴¹ Jarret M Brachman, *Global Jihadism: Theory and practice* (London: Taylor & Francis, 2014), 112-13. Moussalli, *Ibid*, 8-10. Ruthven, *Ibid*, 412-413.

⁴² Nadjma Yassari and Mohammad Hamid Saboory, "Sharia and national law in Afghanistan", in *Sharia incorporated: A comparative overview of the legal systems of Twelve Muslim countries in past and present*, edited by Jan Michiel Otto (Leiden: Amsterdam University Press, 2010), 290-292.

Rise of international Jihadist-terrorism

In the 1990s, jihadist attacks focused more on civilians in and outside of Muslim lands. Bin Laden had denounced the Saudi-Arabian monarchy for allowing American troops within the country during the Gulf war (1990-1991), after which he released several fatwa's declaring war against the United States for their military presence and policy in Muslim lands and their support for Israel, and declared all American and Israeli citizens as legitimate targets.⁴³ Al-Qaeda organized several plots and attacks on American targets, including the 1993 World Trade Center bombing and the 1998 Nairobi embassy bombing.⁴⁴ The Egyptian Jihadist group, who also participated in several al-Qaeda bombings, staged multiple attacks on Egyptian intellectuals, politicians, and tourists. With the number of people killed reaching over 1200, and the consequent devastation of the tourist industry, the Jihadist groups lost support from the Egyptian public. The majority of the group's members were imprisoned and, partly through the mediation of al-Azhar scholars who deradicalized many of the leading members, a deal was struck with the Egyptian government in 1997 where *al-Jama'a al-Islamiyya* renounced all violence. Not all of its members agreed with this deal, and several of them, including Ayman al-Zawahiri, joined al-Qaeda.⁴⁵

The western experience of Islamist-Jihadism underwent a paradigm shift with the World Trade Center attack on 11 September 2001, whereby post-Cold War history is viewed

⁴³ Brachman, *Ibid*, 56. Fawaz A. Gerges, *The rise and fall of Al-Qaeda* (New York: Oxford University Press, 2011), 55. Niaz A. Shah, *Self-defense in Islamic and international law: Assessing Al-Qaeda and the invasion of Iraq* (United Kingdom: Palgrave Macmillan, 2008), 48–53. Moussalli, *Ibid*, 10. Rudolph Peters, *Jihad in classical and modern Islam: A documentary reader: Updated with a section on the jihad in the 21st century*, 2nd ed. (United States: Wiener, Markus Publishers, 2005), 171–83.

⁴⁴ Gerges, *Ibid*, 67, 224-225.

⁴⁵ Springer, Regens, and Edger, *Ibid*, 65. Gerges, *Ibid*, 37-38.

from a pre-and post-9/11 perspective.⁴⁶ After the Cold War, several Western political analysts perceived Islam as the cause for a new ‘clash of civilizations’⁴⁷, which for many was confirmed by the 9/11 attacks. Almost all major Islamic institutions, scholars and political leaders in the Muslim world denounced the 9/11 attacks as unIslamic, as it is forbidden in classical Islam to kill non-combatants or for a small group to declare Jihad in name of the whole Muslim world.⁴⁸ The United States invaded Afghanistan a few months later, after its demand to turn over al-Qaeda was refused by the Taliban, and was aided by NATO allies shortly after. It also led an Allied coalition in invading Iraq which it accused of both aiding al-Qaeda and being in the possession of active weapons of mass destruction, but in both cases this proved untrue. Although Iraq’s leader, Saddam Hussein, had used chemical weapons against Kurdish minorities in 1988, killing up to 5,000 and injuring thousands more, by 2003 his chemical weapons program had fallen into disuse and had long been inactive.

Within a few months the Iraqi regime was defeated and an interim government installed to draft a constitution and guide the transition towards a democratic government. The majority of the old regime’s party members, government services personnel, and members of the military, who were predominantly Sunni, were decommissioned. As a response to what they deemed as an American invasion of Muslim lands, several Sunni and Shia militias formed to drive away the Americans. One of these militias was the Iraqi branch of al-Qaeda led by the Jordanian Abu Musab al-Zarqawi (d. 2006), who also attacked Shia civilians and

⁴⁶ Tibi, *Ibid*, 217.

⁴⁷ *Ibid*, 218-222.

⁴⁸ For an overview, see: Charles Kurzman, *Islamic Statements Against Terrorism*, accessed 10-03-2016, <http://kurzman.unc.edu/islamic-statements-against-terrorism/>.

holy places.⁴⁹ After the 2005 elections a coalition was formed between different political parties, which were dominated by Shia parties. But Shia militias such as the Mahdi Army, the military wing of cleric Muqtada al-Sadr's political movement, deemed the elections as invalid and continued to clash with Iraqi security forces. The Mahdi Army has also been accused of atrocities against Sunni civilians.⁵⁰

From 2000 on, other Muslim-majority countries or regions such as Chechnya, Yemen, Kashmir (e.g. *Jaish-e-Mohammad*), the Maghreb (i.e. Libya, Tunisia, Algeria, Morocco and Saharan communities including the Tuareg and Mali tribes), and Somalia (e.g. al-Shabaab) had militias who cooperated with or pledged allegiance to al-Qaeda, and conducted attacks and kidnappings. Several major attacks have been claimed by or linked to al-Qaeda, including those in Djerba (Tunisia, 2002), Bali (2002), Riyadh (2003), Casablanca (2003), Jakarta (2003), Istanbul (2003), Madrid (2004), London (2005), the assassination of presidential candidate Benazir Bhutto in Pakistan (2007), Islamabad (2008), Mumbai (2008) and Pune (India, 2010).⁵¹

Rise of ISIS

In 2010 a series of protests, starting in Tunisia crossed over to other Muslim countries, including Libya, Egypt, Syria, Yemen, Iran, and Bahrain. These protests turned into revolutions, resulting in what was called the Arab Spring, which ousted the rulers of Tunisia

⁴⁹ Shah, *Ibid*, 164. Cole Bunzel, "From paper state to Caliphate: The ideology of the Islamic state", *The Brookings Project on U.S. Relations with the Islamic World* 19 (2015): 13–16, accessed juli 6, 2016, <http://www.brookings.edu/~media/research/files/papers/2015/03/ideology-of-islamic-state-bunzel/the-ideology-of-the-islamic-state.pdf>.

⁵⁰ BBC, "Falluja: Iraqi Shia militia 'killed and seized civilians'", *BBC Middle East* (BBC News), juli 5, 2016, <http://www.bbc.co.uk/news/world-middle-east-36716494>.

⁵¹ "Al Qaeda attacks: A chronology", oktober 19, 2011, accessed juli 6, 2016, <http://channel.nationalgeographic.com/explorer/articles/al-qaeda-attacks-a-chronology/>. Andrew Wander, "A history of terror: Al-Qaeda 1988-2008", *The Guardian* (The Guardian), juli 13, 2008, <https://www.theguardian.com/world/2008/jul/13/history.alqaida>.

(Zine El Abidine Ben Ali), Egypt (Hosni Mubarak), Yemen (Ali Abdullah Saleh), and Libya (Muammar Gaddafi) within a few years. Countries such as Kuwait, Lebanon, Oman, Morocco and Jordan, made governmental or constitutional changes to appease the protesters. Tunisia, Egypt, and Libya formed interim governments to draft new constitutions and prepare for elections. In Syria protests spread over large cities, whereby the regime responded with shootings and mass arrests. Opposition forces formed resistance militias, secular and Islamist, who mostly aligned themselves as the Free Syrian Army.⁵² Several Jihadist groups, including some aligned to al-Qaeda also joined the fighting, whereby they attracted many non-Syrian fighters, especially from Europe and North-Africa. One of these groups was the Iraqi branch of al-Qaeda who after conquering an area in Syria in 2013 declared it had established an Islamic state in the area and which it called *al-Dawlah al-Islamiyyah fi al-Iraq wa al-Sham* (The Islamic State in Iraq and the Levant, ISIS). Its leader, Ibrahim al-Badri (using the nickname Abu Bakr al-Baghdadi), had succeeded the previous leader of al-Qaeda in Iraq (which called themselves the “Islamic State of Iraq”) in 2010, and was part of its organization since 2006. Before that al-Badri was the founder of a Jihadist group in 2003 as a response to the Allied invasion of Iraq. He was imprisoned in an American internment camp between 2005-2009, where he met other Jihadist leaders as well as officials who had held positions in Saddam’s army and party (the secular Ba’ath party). Several of them joined his al-Qaeda group and became chiefs of intelligence and military operations, and were vital for the later rapid expansion of ISIS. When ISIS declared its establishment of the state (also changing its

⁵² For an overview of each Arab Spring rising, see: David W. Lesch and Mark L. Haas, red., *The Arab spring: Change and resistance in the middle east* (United States: Westview Press, 2012). Muriel Asseburg, *Protest, revolt and regime change in the Arab world. Actors, challenges, implications and policy options*, (n.p., 2012), https://www.swp-berlin.org/fileadmin/contents/products/research_papers/2012_RP06_ass.pdf. “Protest, uprising & regime change in the Arab spring”, Arab Spring, januari 28, 2014, accessed juli 31, 2016, <http://muftah.org/protest-uprising-revolution-regime-change-explaining-outcomes-arab-spring/#.V526x1dUdCk>.

name to *Dawlah al-Islamiyyah*, IS), other al-Qaeda leaders (e.g. Abu Muhammad al-Julani, Ayman al-Zawahiri, leader of al-Qaeda since the death of Bin Laden in 2011) rejected their claim as unlawful, and al-Zawahiri demanded an oath of allegiance from al-Baghdadi which he declined, resulting in hostility between the Jihadist groups. ISIS also conquered areas in Iraq and expanded rapidly, attracting more foreign fighters and fighters from other Jihadist groups.⁵³

On June 29 of 2014, ninety years after the abolition of the Ottoman Caliphate, ISIS took the bold step of claiming it had re-established the Caliphate, through which it demanded allegiance from all Muslims around the world as a religious obligation.⁵⁴ It persecuted and enslaved the Yazidis, a religious minority, which it deemed apostates and thus not liable for religious protective taxes (the *Jizyah*) as asked from Christians living in their controlled area. ISIS destroyed tombs, churches, mosques and archeological sites which it deemed idolatrous, although they at the same time sold many antiques on the black market. The group gained their reputation for brutality most for their harsh punishments and executions in their controlled areas⁵⁵, as well as through professionally edited graphic propaganda videos where Muslims and non-Muslims (Arabs and non-Arabs) were executed as forms of revenge for or

⁵³ Bunzel, *Ibid*, 13-30.

⁵⁴ *Ibid*, 31-32.

⁵⁵ On ISIS' idea and application of law and economy, see: Mara Revkin, "ISIS Taxation and public finance", june 16, 2015, accessed juli 6, 2016, <https://mararevkin.wordpress.com/2015/06/16/isis-taxation-and-public-finance/>. Andrew F. March and Mara Revkin, "Caliphate of law", april 15, 2015, accessed july 6, 2016, <https://mararevkin.wordpress.com/2015/04/15/caliphate-of-law/>. On their human rights abuses, see: The Clarion Project, *Special Report: The Islamic State*, (n.p., 2015), 26-30, <https://www.clarionproject.org/sites/default/files/islamic-state-isis-isil-factsheet-1.pdf>. ISIS also proudly displays these acts in their media outlets such as their English magazine 'Dabiq': "The Islamic state's (ISIS, ISIL) magazine", september 10, 2014, accessed july 7, 2016, <http://www.clarionproject.org/news/islamic-state-isis-isil-propaganda-magazine-dabiq>.

threats against local enemies and Western intervention.⁵⁶ Because of the rapid success of ISIS other Jihadist groups as Boko Haram (Nigeria) and others in Libya, Yemen, Algeria, Chechnya, Philippines, Egypt, and Pakistan, claimed allegiance to them.⁵⁷

In 2012, an al-Qaeda aligned Tuareg group (Ansar Dine) conquered parts of Mali where they imposed their version of the Sharia and destroyed tombs of Muslim saints, before being ousted by the French army.⁵⁸ In the beginning of 2015 several terrorist attacks were performed by al-Qaeda (e.g. Charlie Hebdo magazine in Paris, France, and Garissa college, Kenya) which were deemed as attacks to show al-Qaeda still was the main Jihadist group.⁵⁹ ISIS, meanwhile, called on Muslims to attack non-Muslims everywhere to create havoc and fear. Several professional attacks, including the 2015 bombing of a Russian airliner killing 224, a bombing in Lebanon killing 43, and a carefully orchestrated attack on Paris restaurants, bars, concert hall, and stadium killing 130, were claimed by ISIS, as well as ‘lone wolf’ attacks whereby attackers personally claimed allegiance to ISIS without consulting them on it (e.g. 2015 Sousse, Tunisia).⁶⁰ As of the beginning of 2016, several Western and Arab countries have joined together in an alliance to bomb ISIS⁶¹, while Russia and Iran supports

⁵⁶ Hassan, *Ibid*, 17-19. The Clarion Project, *Ibid*, 19-22.

⁵⁷ The Clarion Project, *Ibid*, 23.

⁵⁸ “Geography in the news: Al Qaeda and Tuareg in Mali”, januari 15, 2013, accessed juli 6, 2016, <http://voices.nationalgeographic.com/2013/01/15/geography-in-the-news-al-qaeda-and-tuareg-in-mali/>.

⁵⁹ Anne Barnard and Neil Macfarquhar, “Paris and Mali attacks expose lethal Qaeda-ISIS rivalry”, Middle East (The New York Times), april 29, 2016, <http://www.nytimes.com/2015/11/21/world/middleeast/paris-and-mali-attacks-expose-a-lethal-al-qaeda-isis-rivalry.html>.

⁶⁰ “ISIS Timeline: Sunni Militants unleash terror around the world”, augustus 7, 2015, accessed juli 6, 2016, <http://www.infoplease.com/world/events/isis-timeline.html>. “Timeline: Rise and spread of the Islamic state”, juli 6, 2016, accessed juli 6, 2016, <https://www.wilsoncenter.org/article/timeline-rise-and-spread-the-islamic-state>.

⁶¹ Erika Solomon and Geoff Dyer, “Middle East: The factions behind the fight against Isis”, *Financial Times*, May 23 2016, <https://next.ft.com/content/c1e5ccca-1e6a-11e6-b286-cddde55ca122>.

the Syrian regime, which is behind the majority of civilian casualties, by bombing all opposition forces.⁶²

Overview of anti-terrorism Fatwa's

From the beginning of jihadist attacks inside and outside Muslim lands, the majority of Muslim scholars have rejected their methods and claims of it being a legitimate Jihad as proscribed by the Sharia.⁶³ Technically Jihad, as in warfare, becomes an obligation for individual Muslims when Muslim lands are attacked, thus scholars argue it is primarily to be employed only for defensive purposes.⁶⁴ As stated in the introduction, when Western forces colonized the majority of Muslim lands in the 19th and early 20th century, many resistance movements were deemed legitimate in their claim of Jihad. Several late 20th and early 21st century conflicts were seen as attacks on Muslim lands and so fighting in defense of those lands was considered by resistance fighters to be a legitimate cause for Jihad. But many Jihadist groups applied tactics and targets that scholars have deemed as unlawful according to Sharia law, which, in contrast to claims of the leaders of groups such as al-Qaeda and ISIS, stipulates that women, children, elderly, sick, clergy, ambassadors, and non-combatants may never be killed.⁶⁵ With the increased use of bombs and Muslim victims (the majority of al-

⁶² Aron Lund, *Stand together or fall apart: The Russian-Iranian alliance in Syria*, (Carnegie Endowment for International Peace), 2016, <http://carnegieendowment.org/syriaincrisis/?fa=63699>.

⁶³ Kurzman, *Ibid. Condemnations of suicide bombing by Muslims*, (ABC news: Ihsanic-intelligence.com), <https://www.abc.se/home/m9783/ir/ez/isl/0-sbm/Condemnations%20of%20Suicide%20Bombing%20by%20Muslims.pdf>.

⁶⁴ For a general overview on classical rulings on Jihad, see: Ahmed Al-Dawoody, *The Islamic Law of War: Justifications and Regulations* (New York: Palgrave Macmillan, 2011). Reuven Firestone, *Jihād: The Origin of Holy War in Islam* (New York: Oxford University Press, 1999).

⁶⁵ Al-Dawoody, *Ibid*, 111-116.

Qaeda victims are Muslim⁶⁶) and noncombatant non-Muslim victims, many notable Muslim scholars declared fatwa's against the Jihadi groups' methods and claims. After 9/11, the majority of Muslim institutions, scholars, and political leaders, denounced the attack. Also with the increase of Islamophobia against Muslims globally, but especially against Muslim minorities in the West, public condemnations of Muslim terrorism increased.

In 2004 the first global consensus (the Amman Message) among Muslim scholars in the history of Islam declared that it was forbidden to excommunicate other Muslims, Sunni or Shia.⁶⁷ This consensus was sought as a response to the excommunication of Shia and Sufi Muslims by Sunni extremists, especially by groups active in Iraq. Although Sunni extremists keep excommunicating and attacking Shia Muslims, the consensus was mostly meant to influence general Muslim discourse, especially the preaching of Wahhabi and Salafi scholars.⁶⁸

In 2010, a famous Pakistani scholar, Muhammad Tahir-ul-Qadri, who is deemed a 'shaykh al-Islam' which is considered to belong to one of the highest ranks of Islamic scholarship, issued a 400 page fatwa against terrorism and suicide bombings, which was

⁶⁶ Yassin Musharbash, "Surprising study on terrorism: Al-Qaida kills Eight times more Muslims than Non-Muslims", Spiegel Online, december 3, 2009, <http://www.spiegel.de/international/world/surprising-study-on-terrorism-al-qaida-kills-eight-times-more-muslims-than-non-muslims-a-660619.html>. Institute for Economics and Peace, *Global Terrorism Index*, (n.p., 2015), <http://economicsandpeace.org/wp-content/uploads/2015/11/Global-Terrorism-Index-2015.pdf>.

⁶⁷ The Amman Message (2004), accessed december 7, 2015, www.ammannmessage.com.

⁶⁸ "The Amman message and intra-muslim peace | middle east", 2016, accessed july 7, 2016, <http://www.crpme.gr/analysis/middle-east/the-ammann-message-and-intra-muslim-peace>. Jamal Al Shalabi en Menawer Bayan Alrajehi, "The Amman message: Arab diplomacy in the dialogue of civilizations", *Journal of US-China Public Administration* 8, no. 12 (2012), accessed july 7, 2016, <http://www.davidpublishing.com/davidpublishing/Upfile/2/18/2012/2012021808754238.pdf>.

translated into several languages.⁶⁹ It is the largest fatwa text denouncing terrorism⁷⁰, but also the first to be simultaneously available in English and Arabic. In the fatwa he discusses the unlawfulness of indiscriminately killing Muslims and non-Muslims, the obligation of protection and rights of noncombatant non-Muslims, the unlawfulness of rebelling against the state, and deeming violent rebels to belong to the Kharijites.⁷¹ This last part is a theme which has become vital in modern Islamic denunciations of terrorism. The Kharijites (lit. the leavers, as in leaving the Muslim community) were a rebel group in early Islam who had killed the 3rd and 4th successor (*khalif*) of the Prophet Muhammad. For two centuries they plagued the main Muslim community with violent attacks whereby they deemed the majority of Muslims to be unbelievers.⁷² To label contemporary Jihadist groups as Kharijite provides Muslim scholars a label that is recognizable for fellow Muslims in how to view these

⁶⁹ Muhammad Tahir-ul-Qadri, *Fatwa on terrorism and suicide bombings* (United Kingdom: Minhaj-ul-Quran International (MQI) UK, 2010). Available at: <http://www.quranandwar.com/FATWA%20on%20Terrorism%20and%20Suicide%20Bombings.pdf>.

⁷⁰ I hope to provide a more extensive analysis of this fatwa in the future, which can be considered the most thorough and extensive referenced Fiqh critique of terrorism currently written. Some of its claims, such on the meaning of Islam as meaning ‘safety for all of humanity’, can be considered as modern concepts, but the majority of its statements on war ethics and politics are representative of classical Sunnism (although these are mainly referenced from the Hanafi school) and deserve a larger review. He also launched an “Islamic Curriculum on Peace and Counter-Terrorism” in 2015 to counter ISIS ideology, wherein he provides reading manuals for Islamic schools and mosques. Minhaj-ul-Quran International, *Dr Tahir-ul-Qadri launches Islamic curriculum on peace and counter-terrorism in UK*, (Minhaj-ul-Quran International), juni 23, 2015, <http://www.minhaj.org/english/tid/33354/Dr-Tahir-ul-Qadri-launches-anti-ISIS-Islamic-curriculum-peace-counter-terrorism-de-radicalisation-ideology-Jihad-elimination-extremism-UK.html>.

⁷¹ Tahir-ul-Qadri, *Ibid*, 385-396.

⁷² “[T]he members of the earliest of the religious sects of Islam, whose importance lies particularly, from the point of view of the development of dogma, in the formulation of questions relative to the theory of the caliphate and to justification by faith or by works, while from the point of view of political history the principal part they played was disturbing by means of continual insurrections, which often ended in the temporary conquest of entire provinces, the peace of the eastern part of the Muslim empire during the two last years of the caliphate of ‘Alī and during the Umayyad period, and involuntarily facilitating first Mu‘āwiya’s victory over ‘Alī, then that of the ‘Abbāsids over the Umayyads.” G. Levi Della Vida, “*Khāridjites*”, in: *Encyclopaedia of Islam, Second Edition*, edited by: P. Bearman, Th. Bianquis, C.E. Bosworth, E. van Donzel, W.P. Heinrichs, accessed on 08 July 2016, http://dx.doi.org.ezproxy.leidenuniv.nl:2048/10.1163/1573-3912_islam_COM_0497.

groups.⁷³ But there is disagreement on if this label can be used to excommunicate terrorists or not (*takfir*, i.e. their actions nullify their faith adherence)⁷⁴, or that they are major sinners (*fasiq*) but still recognized as being Muslim.⁷⁵

⁷³ Shmuel Bar, *The religious sources of Islamic terrorism*, (Hoover Institution), June 1, 2004, <http://www.hoover.org/research/religious-sources-islamic-terrorism>. Nelly Lahoud, "The early Kharijites and their understanding of Jihād", *Mélanges de l'Université Saint-Joseph* LXII (2009), accessed July 6, 2016, <https://www.ctc.usma.edu/posts/the-early-kharijites-and-their-understanding-of-jihad>. Islam against Extremism, *The Khārijites: Historical Roots Of Modern-Day extremism And Terrorism*, (n.p., 2015), <http://www.islamagainstextremism.com/dld.cfm?a=qxufgu>.

⁷⁴ Tahir-ul-Qadri dedicated a whole chapter on citations from classical scholars on declaring Kharijites as unbelievers. Tahir-ul-Qadri, *Ibid*, 351-384. Tahir-ul-Qadri has repeated this excommunication (*takfir*) also concerning ISIS. The same is done by Shaykh Muhammad al-Yaqoubi in his fatwa against ISIS, see below.

⁷⁵ This issue has confused many lay Muslims and non-Muslims alike, due to their misunderstanding of classical Sunnism's approach to faith-adherence, which in many ways resembles Catholic concepts of baptism. Every time a prominent Catholic Nazi had passed away, a controversy arises when certain Catholic groups (to the embarrassment of the Vatican) still provided him his funeral rites, which includes prayers of forgiveness and acceptance by God into heaven. In post-WWII thought this act is misunderstood as a form of Catholic acceptance or whitewashing of the person's crimes (although there are certainly Catholic groups with Nazi/anti-Semitic sympathies), while from a Catholic theological perspective this service is connected to the sacramental status of the person's baptism. Daniel Burke, "Catholic sect holds funeral rites for Nazi war criminal", *CNN*, October 15, 2013, <http://religion.blogs.cnn.com/2013/10/15/nazi-war-criminal-to-get-church-burial/>. Classical Sunnism, although it does not accept the idea of sacramental theology, has a similar approach to faith-adherence. The testimony of faith (*Shahada*) is what one brings into Islam, and only clear and self-expressed declarations that reject that earlier testimony is what brings one out of Islam. Ethical and ritual misconduct are sinful (from small to larger sins) and makes one a sinner (*Fasiq*), but do not necessarily nullify one's faith-adherence due to the separation of faith (*iman*) and acts (*'amal*) as separate ontological categories. Anyone who declared the *Shahada* but upholds beliefs deviating from the orthodox mainstream is an heretical innovator (*Mubtadi*) and not an unbeliever (*Kafir*). Acts are based on perception (*Mudarak*) and piety (*Taqwa*) and it is these two that can fluctuate in a believer and can make one commit evil or good deeds. Only large, clear, non-compulsory and continued acts of idolatry (*Shirk*) in worship (*ibadat*), which belong to other religions, can make one an unbeliever as this would be a continued rejection of Islamic monotheism (*Tawhid*) and/or the prophethood of Muhammad. Personal sins as drinking or lapses in obligatory prayers are personal sins, not rejections of monotheism or Muhammad's prophethood. This separation of belief and acts was a reaction towards the Kharijites themselves who judged Muslims only on their acts and not on their words of faith. For them, belief is shown by deeds, thus when deeds are lacking (like praying), one can be declared an unbeliever. On the classical separation of faith and acts, see: Imam Al-Haramayn Al-Juywani, *A guide to conclusive Proofs for the principles of belief: Kitab Al-Irshad Ila Qawati Al-Adilla Fi Usul Ati Tiqad*, translated by Paul E. Walker (United Kingdom: Garnet Publishing, 2001), 209–15. Ahmad Farid al-Mazidi, Ed., *Shuruh wa Hawashi al-'Aqa'id al-Nasafiyya li-Ahl al-Sunna wa-Ijama'a al-Asha'ira wa-Imaturidiyya* (Beirut: Dar al-Kutub al-'Ilmiyya, 2013), 5:3–89. Ibn Abi al-'Izz, *Commentary on the Creed of at-Tahawi (Sharh al-'Aqidah at-Tahawiyah)*, translated by Muhammad 'Abdul-Haqq Ansari (Riyadh: al-Imam Muhammad Ibn Sa'ud Islamic University, 2000), 283–311. On modern rejections of excommunicating terrorists, see for example: Hamza Yusuf, "Suicide bombers are still Muslim", *YouTube*, April 22, 2013, posted July 13, 2016, <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=2Zhi8bED9o0>. With the anti-ISIS fatwa's a similar discussion (and controversy) arises when certain Islamic scholars or institutions condemn their acts, but reject to excommunicate them. See below for further discussions on this.

Letter to Baghdadi: A new Sunni consensus against Islamist-Jihadism?

Background of the Letter

With the rise of ISIS, new fatwa's were produced that not only condemned their attacks, but also their claim of being a Caliphate.⁷⁶ One 40 page fatwa-letter⁷⁷, addressed to al-Baghdadi and his followers, and was signed by more than 120 prominent Muslim scholars (including Tahir-ul-Qadri).⁷⁸ The majority of signatory scholars have an Egyptian background, and many are part of or have directly studied at al-Azhar or have been influenced by major Azhari reformist scholars such Mahmud al-Shaltut (d. 1963).⁷⁹

⁷⁶ Mandhai, "Muslim leaders reject Baghdadi's caliphate", *Al Jazeera Media Network*, July 7, 2014, <http://www.aljazeera.com/news/middleeast/2014/07/muslim-leaders-reject-baghdadi-caliphate-20147744058773906.html>.

⁷⁷ It calls itself a letter (*risala*) and not a fatwa, as normally a fatwa responds to a question on a legal issue or situation requiring a legal opinion. As this letter is addressed to ISIS based on the initiative of the signatory scholars, it is technically not a fatwa, even though it contains legal opinions and verdicts. The interesting aspect is that it calls itself an 'open letter (*risala maftuha*)', whereby the Arabic is more a translation of the English term than the other way around. Letters between scholars or from scholars to rulers or groups have a long history in Islam. For example: 1) From scholar to ruler: Michael Schwarz, "The Letter of al-Hasan al-Basri", *Oriens* 20 (1967), doi:10.2307/1580396; 2) Between Muslim scholars: "A Letter to Imām al-rāzī", accessed July 11, 2016, <http://www.ibnarabisociety.org/articles/Letter-to-imam-al-razi.html>. But the Letter does end with a fatwa which discusses the authenticity and interpretation of an eschatological tradition attributed to Ali, and which the Letter directly links to ISIS. Letter, *Ibid*, 26-27.

⁷⁸ *Open Letter To Dr. Ibrahim Awwad Al-Badri, alias 'Abu Bakr Al-Baghdadi', and to the fighters and followers of the self-declared 'Islamic State'* (2014), accessed July 6, 2016, www.lettertobaghdadi.com.

⁷⁹ For a discussion on Azhar modernism, see: Kate Zebiri, *Mahmud Shaltut and Islamic modernism* (United Kingdom: Oxford University Press, 1993). Malika Zeghal, "Religion and politics in Egypt: The Ulema of Al-Azhar, radical Islam, and the state (1952–94)", *International Journal of Middle East Studies* 31, no. 03 (August 1999), doi:10.1017/s0020743800055483. Samira Haj, *Reconfiguring Islamic tradition: Reform, rationality, and modernity* (United States: Stanford University Press, 2008). Jonathan A. C. Brown, *Misquoting Muhammad: The challenge and choices of interpreting the prophet's legacy* (United Kingdom: Oneworld Publications, 2014), 133–39. Thomas Raineau, "Islamic reform and conservatism. Al-Azhar and the evolution of modern Sunni Islam", *Arabica* 58, no. 5 (January 1, 2011), doi:10.1163/157005811x575889.

Figure 1. Continent of residence ‘Letter to Baghdadi’ signatories

The original website and the Arabic and English PDF’s of the Letter used simple designs, but after around 6 months both the website and the PDF’s were redesigned. The PDF’s redesign directly showed a link with the Jordanian neo-traditionalist⁸⁰, ecumenical (the Amman Message) and interfaith projects by the Royal Islamic Strategic Studies Centre (RISSC), which is sponsored and headed by the Jordanian monarchy.⁸¹ After its redesign,

⁸⁰ Its neo-traditionalism mixes Sunni traditional *Sufi-Madhabism* with Sunni modernism, for a discussion on these spectrums of Islamic modernism, traditionalism to radicalism, see: William E. Shepard, “Islam and ideology: Towards a typology”, *International Journal of Middle East Studies* 19, no. 03 (augustus 1987), doi:10.1017/s0020743800056750.

⁸¹ “Royal Islamic Strategic Studies Centre”, may 15, 2016, accessed july 7, 2016, <http://rissc.jo/>. The organization is responsible for the 2004 Sunni-Shi’a ecumenical ‘Amman Message’, the 2006 Muslim-Christian interfaith ‘A Common Word’ (www.acommonword.com), the ‘Muslim 500’, multiple publications in Arabic and English on normative Sunni Islamic positions on war and politics, and an Arabic-English online resource website for Qur’anic exegesis (www.altafsir.com). It’s director is Prince Ghazi bin Muhammad Talal, the brother of the Jordanian king Abdullah II. See Appendix I for a comparison between the original and redesigned PDF of the Letter and the RISSC publications. Nowhere does the Letter refer to RISSC, or the RISSC websites to the Letter.

several signatories were placed prominently on the website, which shows a focus on scholars from Egypt, America, Nigeria, and Indonesia.⁸² Its press release was done through multiple organizations and persons⁸³, but without specific persons being appointed as the main writers. But both the style and content of the Letter clearly show a similarity with al-Azhar on creedal position towards the relation of faith and acts, inner-*Madhab* pluralism, penal punishments (*Hudud*) and civil law⁸⁴, and Jihad.⁸⁵ The Letter's position on slavery being abolished has also been professed by al-Azhar.⁸⁶, but by saying its abolishment is through 'worldly consensus' is clearly a contribution by Shaykh Muhammad al-Yaqoubi who has expounded on this issue in his own fatwa (discussed below) and in interviews.⁸⁷ The Letter is therefore probably written by scholar(s) trained at (and some still affiliated with) al-Azhar, and scholars surrounding

⁸² These are: Prof. Sheikh Shawqi Allam: The Grand Mufti of Egypt; Sheikh Dr. Ali Gomaa: Former Grand Mufti of Egypt; Sheikh Hamza Yusuf Hanson: Founder and Director of Zaytuna College, USA; Dr. Muhammad Tahir Al-Qadri: Founder of Minhaj-ul-Qur'an International, Pakistan; Dr. Yasir Qadhi: Professor of Islamic Studies, Rhodes College, USA; Sheikh Faraz Rabani: Islamic Scholar and Founder of Seekers Guidance, Canada; Sultan Muhammad Sa'ad Ababakar: The Sultan of Sokoto, Head of the Nigerian National Supreme Council for Islamic Affairs; Prince Judge Bola AbdulJabbar Ajibola: Islamic Mission for Africa (IMA) and Founder of Crescent University, Nigeria; Sheikh Ibrahim Saleh Al-Husseini: Head of the Supreme Council for Fatwa and Islamic Affairs, Nigeria; Prof. M. Din Syamsuddin: President of Muhammadiyah, and Chairman of the Indonesian Council of Ulama.

⁸³ Lauren Markoe, "Muslim scholars to Islamic state: You don't understand Islam", *Huffington Post* (The Huffington Post), september 24, 2014, http://www.huffingtonpost.com/2014/09/24/muslim-scholars-islamic-state_n_5878038.html. "'Risala miftuha ila 'al-Baghdadi'", accessed juli 8, 2016, <http://www.ammonnews.net/mobile/index.php?page=article&id=207096>.

⁸⁴ "Applying Shari'ah in today's world", accessed juli 8, 2016, <http://eng.dar-alifta.org/foreign/ViewArticle.aspx?ID=109&text=hudud>. "Shariah law", accessed juli 8, 2016, <http://eng.dar-alifta.org/foreign/ViewArticle.aspx?ID=111&text=civil%20law>. "Juristic differences in Sharia", 2016, accessed juli 8, 2016, <http://eng.dar-alifta.org/foreign/ViewArticle.aspx?ID=76&text=increase>. "Ḥudūd in the Islamic Sharia", accessed juli 8, 2016, <http://eng.dar-alifta.org/foreign/ViewArticle.aspx?ID=358&text=jihad>.

⁸⁵ "Jihad: Concept, history and contemporary application", accessed juli 8, 2016, <http://eng.dar-alifta.org/foreign/ViewArticle.aspx?ID=78&text=jihad>.

⁸⁶ "Fatawa - why didn't Islam abolish slavery immediately?", 2016, accessed juli 8, 2016, <http://eng.dar-alifta.org/foreign/ViewFatwa.aspx?ID=6830>.

⁸⁷ "Sheikh Muhammad al-yaqoubi responds to al-julani's al-jazeera interview", mei 31, 2015, accessed juli 8, 2016, <http://www.joshualandis.com/blog/sheikh-muhammad-al-yaqoubi-responds-to-al-julanis-al-jazeera-interview/>.

Shaykh Muhammad al-Yaqoubi and Shaykh Bin Bayyah such as Hamza Yusuf. We will provide more examples to assess this author-probability below.

Analysis of the Letter to Baghdadi

All the signatories are Sunni⁸⁸ and the Letter doesn't discuss the signatories' position towards the Muslim status of the Shi'a, nor does it refer to the Amman Message. Seemingly it avoids taking in an ecumenical position, as ISIS' Jihadi-Salafism sees accepting Shi'a as Muslims as something which makes one an unbeliever. This position, and others such as the rejection of civil laws and *irja* creedal positions⁸⁹, belong to the Wahhabi-Salafi creedal concept of 'Nullifiers of Islam (*Nawaqid al-Islam*)'.⁹⁰ Although the Letter avoids the discussion on Shi'ism, it does address the questions pertaining to excommunication (*takfir*), pluralism, Shari'a and civil law, democracy, Jihad, and how these pertain to modern Muslim-majority countries and Muslims living in the west. The Letter also states that their statements

⁸⁸ None of the signatories belong to Wahhabi or radical Salafi ideologies, all adhere to a spectrum between Sunni neo-traditionalism and modernism. There are also no signatories from Saudi-Arabia. Also it is interesting that famous scholars as the Muslim Brotherhood ideologue Yusuf al-Qaradawi are not among the signatories. This is maybe due to the conflict between al-Azhar and the Muslim Brotherhood after the military coup against president Morsi.

⁸⁹ The Murji'a (lit. postponers or deferrers) were an early Sunni theological movement who radically separated faith (*iman*) from acts (*'amal*), whereby no act could make one be declared an unbeliever, as only God could truly judge (whereby they thus postpone the judgement to God alone). Some Murji'a also believed to there was no sin heavy enough performed by a believer to be placed in hell. The Athari-traditionalists and Ash'ari theologians took an opposite position whereby one's faith is expressed and affected by one acts, and therefore faith could increase or decrease. The Hanafi-Maturidi theologians did uphold elements of the Murji'a due to the creedal statements of the Hanafi school founder Abu Hanifa (d. 772) that faith cannot increase or decrease. Abu Hanifa was also accused of being a Murji'a by several Athari scholars such as the Hadith collector al-Bukhari (d. 870). See also above at fn. 75. Wilfred Madelung, "Murjī'a", in: *Encyclopaedia of Islam*, Second Edition, edited by: P. Bearman, Th. Bianquis, C.E. Bosworth, E. van Donzel, W.P. Heinrichs, accessed 08 July 2016, http://dx.doi.org/ezproxy.leidenuniv.nl:2048/10.1163/1573-3912_islam_COM_0801.

⁹⁰ ISIS follows the Wahabi-Salafi creedal position of 'Nullifiers of Islam (*Nawaqid al-Islam*)' as stated in the official ISIS creedal text "*Aqidah Wa Manhaj Al-Dawlah Al-Islamiyah Fi Al-Takfir*". Muhammad Haniff Hassan, *A wolf in sheep's clothing: An analysis of ISIS Takfir doctrine*, (counterideology 2), augustus 11, 2015, <https://counterideology2.wordpress.com/2015/08/11/a-wolf-in-sheeps-clothing-an-analysis-of-isis-takfir-doctrine/>. Ella Landau-Tasseron, *A self-profile of the Islamic state: The creedal document*, (Middle East Media Research Institute (MEMRI), 2016), http://www.memri.org/pdf/MEMRI_IA_A_Self-Profile_of_the_Islamic_State-The_Creedal_Document2.pdf.

on these matters represent “the opinions of the overwhelming majority of Sunni scholars over the course of Islamic history.”⁹¹ The Letter considers 24 points which can be classified into seven categories:

- 1) Characteristics (*sifat*) and requirements (*shurut*) of a mufti or *qadi* (judge): points 1-5
- 2) Rulings on warfare (*Ahkam al-Harb*): points 6-8
- 3) Intra-Muslim pluralism (*ikhtilaf*) and apostasy (*takfir* and *ridda*): point 9
- 4) Human rights (*Huquq al-`ibad*) and rulings pertaining to protected minorities (*Ahkam al-Dhimma*): points 10-15
- 5) Requirements of penal law (*Hudud*) and treatment of captives: points 16-18
- 6) Creed (*`aqida*): points 19-20
- 7) Leadership (*imama* and *khilafa*) and loyalty to the umma and rejection of non-believing communities (*al-Wala wa al-Bara*): points 21-24

We will discuss these points using their own summary of the points⁹² which we will analyze here⁹³:

1. It is forbidden in Islam to issue fatwas without all the necessary learning requirements. Even then fatwas must follow Islamic legal theory as defined in the Classical texts. It is also forbidden to cite a portion of a verse from the

⁹¹ Letter, *Ibid*, 3.

⁹² Letter, *Ibid*, 1-2.

⁹³ We will also discuss the review of the Letter written by Ella Landau-Tasserion from the Hebrew University in Jerusalem. Ella Landau-Tasserion *Delegitimizing ISIS On Islamic Grounds: Criticism Of Abu Bakr Al-Baghdadi By Muslim Scholars* (2015), accessed december 20 2015, <http://www.memri.org/report/en/0/0/0/0/0/8873.htm>.

Qur'an—or part of a verse—to derive a ruling without looking at everything that the Qur'an and Hadith teach related to that matter. In other words, there are strict subjective and objective prerequisites for fatwas, and one cannot 'cherry-pick' Qur'anic verses for legal arguments without considering the entire Qur'an and Hadith.⁹⁴

2. It is forbidden in Islam to issue legal rulings about anything without mastery of the Arabic language.⁹⁵

⁹⁴ The Letter begins with the requirements needed to derive and issue legal verdicts. Letter, *Ibid*, 4-5. To start the Letter like this is an indirect accusation that ISIS' scholars and leadership do not fit these requirements. One of ISIS' most prominent mufti's, the young Turki al-Binali, is criticized by many scholars, including his old teachers, that he lacks the qualifications for his position. "ISIS Leader Al-Binali: A terrorist who moves freely", november 29, 2014, accessed juli 11, 2016, <http://mirror.no-ip.org/news/20325.html>. "The Caliphate's Scholar-in-Arms", Jihadica, 2014, accessed juli 11, 2016, <http://www.jihadica.com/the-caliphate%E2%80%99s-scholar-in-arms/>. At the same time this Letter is also aware that the rest of the Muslim world is also a potential audience and therefore provide these short statements on classical hermeneutics to inform a general audience. The Letter cites a short summary on the requirements of Fiqh hermeneutics and being a mufti as viewed by the Shafi'i school. Although it could be argued, as the Letter does, that all schools agree on these principals, technically there are important differences with the Maliki (emphasis Medina practice above singular Hadith) and the Hanafi (preference of Qur'an and analogy (*Qiyas*) above singular Hadith) vis-à-vis the Shafi'i and Hanbali. But to portray such diversity one such key principles would probably play into the hands of extreme Salafi who reject this level of disagreement among the first righteous generations (*Salaf al-Salih*) as inconceivable. For discussions on this, see: Jasser Auda, *Maqasid al-Shari'ah as Philosophy of Islamic Law* (Kuala Lumpur, Malaysia: Islamic Book Trust, 2010), 76–142. Bernard G Weiss, *The Search for God's law: Islamic Jurisprudence in the Writings of Sayf al-Din al-Amidi* (United States: University of Utah Press, U.S., 2010), 675–725. Wahba al-Zuhayli, *Usul al-Fiqh al-Islami* (Damascus: Dar al-Fikr, 2013), 2:434 – 448. See also al-Azhar's discourse on this: Dar al-ifta al-Misriyyah, "The craft of issuing Fatwas", accessed juli 14, 2016, <http://eng.dar-alifta.org/foreign/ViewArticle.aspx?ID=77>.

⁹⁵ Letter, *Ibid*, 5-6. Here the Letter tries to attack ISIS' spoke person, al-Adnani, who has been mocked before on his amateur statements, which provoked ISIS into defending him by releasing a small biography. It is clear from this biography that he wasn't trained in any Islamic science or even sourcetext apart from the Qur'an. "A biography of IS spokesman Abu Muhammad al-adnani as-shami", november 2, 2014, accessed juli 11, 2016, <https://pietervanostaeyen.com/2014/11/02/a-biography-of-is-spokesman-abu-muhammad-al-adnani-as-shami/>. The Letter tries to show Adnani's amateurism by claiming that his reading of Qur'an 24:55, as referring to the political caliphate instead of general succession of the oppressors by the oppressed, is false. The Letter even invokes Ibn Taymiyya (d. 1328) to prove Adnani's false Qur'anic hermeneutics, and refers to al-Tabari (d. 933)'s exegesis. Ibn Taymiyya is of course the main respected scholar of the Salafi-Wahhabi movement, and al-Tabari's work is one of the most respected works of *tafsir*. But this rebuttal false short as many other classical exegetes, including the second most popular exegete among the Salafi-Wahhabi, Ibn Kathir (d. 1373), do link 24:55 to the political caliphate. Seyyed Hossein Nasr e.a., *The Study Quran: A new translation with notes and*

3. It is forbidden in Islam to oversimplify Shari'ah matters and ignore established Islamic sciences.⁹⁶
4. It is permissible in Islam [for scholars] to differ on any matter, except those fundamentals of religion that all Muslims must know.⁹⁷

commentary (United States: HarperOne, 2015), 884. Ibn Kathir al-Damashqi, *Tafsir al-Qur'an al-Azim* (Beirut: Dar al-Kutub al-'ilmiyyah, 2003), 3:281 – 282.

⁹⁶ Letter, *Ibid*, 6-7. Here the Letter rebukes against one of the central issues (neo-)traditional Sunni Islam has with its modernistic offshoots (i.e. Salafi-Wahhabism, and Islamic modernism as Quranism), the rejection of pluralism (*ikhhtilaf*) within the Shari'a and Islamic sciences. By rejecting this pluralism, and the adherence and dependency on that vast tradition (*taqlid*), which is seen as later innovations, the complex and large multitudes within the classical sciences can be overstepped to go directly to the source texts (Qur'an and Sunna). This Islamic 'sola scriptura' and individual access to the sources is one of the main modernistic elements within the conservative Salafi-Wahhabi movement comparable to Protestantism. Waardenburg, *Ibid*, 292-299. Bin Ali, *Ibid*, 63-64.

⁹⁷ Letter, *Ibid*, 7-8. As a continuation of point 3 is the question of acceptable pluralism. The existence of that pluralism directly shows that classical Sunnism applied rational hermeneutics which causes multiple opinions to form. In general Sunnism sees itself as united in sources and hermeneutical principles (*usul*), and allows difference in the extended interpretations and opinions branching out of them (*furu'*). Salafi-Wahhabism rejects both this pluralism and rational hermeneutics and instead claims a literal a-hermeneutical reading of the source texts. Classical Sunnism scripturalized this pluralism by using a Hadith ("Disagreement in my Umma is a mercy") as proof, but this tradition is rejected by Salafi-Wahhabism due to its weak chain of transmission (*isnad*). Interestingly enough, the Letter avoids the discussion on this Hadith and instead focuses on 1) respected scholars as al-Shafi'i accepted praiseworthy difference of opinion, 2) that the best and easiest options should be chosen as this was the Prophetic practice. The latter point is based on multiple Qur'an verses and Hadith, and has always been central in classical Sunni Fiqh as one of its main maxims (*Qawa'id al-Fiqh*). Intisar A. Rabb, *Doubt in Islamic law: A history of legal maxims, interpretation, and Islamic criminal law* (United Kingdom: Cambridge University Press, 2014), 348–58. Mohammad Hashim Kamali, "Legal maxims and other genres of literature in Islamic jurisprudence", *Arab Law Quarterly* 20, no. 1 (march 1, 2006), doi:10.1163/02680550677525429. Mohammad Hashim Kamali, "The Approved and Disapproved Varieties of *R'ay* (Personal Opinion) in Islam", *Journal of Islamic Social Sciences* 7, no. 1 (march 1990). Also here is a clear similarity between the Letter and al-Azhar discourse: Dar al-ifta al-Misriyya, "The diversity of Juristic opinions vs. The extremists' myth of holding the ultimate truth", 2016, accessed juli 14, 2016, <http://eng.dar-alifta.org/foreign/ViewArticle.aspx?ID=688&text=caliph>. Landau-Tasseron criticizes the Letter's use of verses, claiming these are abrogated, which is a tedious claim as there is wide disagreement on which verses are abrogated, but also a general survey of classical Tafsir texts show this not to be a dominant opinion. She mentions the general assumption that verses promoting peaceful propagation have been abrogated by the Jihad verses is far too simplistic and doesn't reflect the complex way classical scholars used and understood the Qur'an as a living and historical text at the same time. Nasr e.a., *The Study Quran*, 691. The Letter's use of Qur'an 2:185 is criticized by her as something that only refers to Muslims and not non-Muslims, which shows her lack of knowledge in how the term "God desires ease" has been used in Fiqh to advance Muslim and non-Muslim welfare universally as part of the *Qawa'id al-Fiqh*. This for example is clearly seen in the Ottoman-Hanafi civil code *al-Majalla*, which mentions this maxim when referring to contracts and trade between Muslims and non-Muslims alike. *The Mejjele: Ottoman Civil Code* (USA, 2016). For a complete overview on the

5. It is forbidden in Islam to ignore the reality of contemporary times when deriving legal rulings.⁹⁸
6. It is forbidden in Islam to kill the innocent.⁹⁹

broadness this maxim was used (thereby also covering subjects which also provides ease to non-Muslims), see: Mustafa Muhammad al-Zuhayli, *Al-Qawa'id Al-Fiqhiya Wa Tatbiqataha Fi Al-Madhahib Al-Arba'ah* (Damascus: Dar al-Fikr, 2006), 257-271. She also makes an unreferenced statement that “conversion was the result of persecution and pressure”, a claim refuted by many studies. See: Milka Levy-Rubin, *Non-Muslims in the early Islamic empire: From surrender to coexistence* (Cambridge: Cambridge University Press, 2011). Anver M. Emon, *Religious pluralism and Islamic law: Dhimmis and Others in the Empire of Law* (United Kingdom: Oxford University Press, 2014), 34-46, 64-75. Landau-Tasseron, *Ibid*, 6. See further discussion on this below at point 10, fn. 103.

⁹⁸ Here the Letter present the term ‘practical jurisprudence (*Fiqh al-Waq'i*)’, a concatenation not normally seen in classical Fiqh literature, but certainly known as a principle. In the Hanafi school, one of the central principles is that “rulings change according to time (*al-Ahkam takhtalif bi-ikhtilaf al-Zaman*)”. As stated by the Damascene-Ottoman mufti Ibn Abidin (d. 1836): “The juristic cases are either established on the basis of a direct text (*sarih al-nass*) [...] or on the basis of *ijtihad* and *ra'y* (juristic reasoning). In most of the cases the *mujtahid* (jurisconsult) develops his legal arguments and judgments on the basis of the ‘urf (‘social’ customs) of his time such that if he was living in a different time he would make a different legal ruling. It is precisely for this reason that they [i.e. classical scholars] said, while discussing the conditions and qualifications required in *ijtihad*, that he [the *mujtahid*] must be well-versed in the local customs and habits (*adat*) of the people. Therefore, many laws change according to changing times (*al-Ahkam takhtalif bi-ikhtilaf al-Zaman*) such that if a law was allowed to remain the same as it was in the first case this would cause great difficulty and harm to the people (*al-mashaqqah wa darar*), and this would be a violation of the universal principles of Shari‘a which are based on the need to make things light and easy (*takhfif wa taysir*).” Muhammad Amin Ibn Abidin, *Majmu‘at Rasa’il Ibn Abidin* (Istanbul/Cairo, 1930), 2:125. In modern times, scholars as Yusuf al-Qaradawi and Tariq Ramadan have used the term to refer to renewal of free interpretation (*ijtihad*) in a more radical way than normally understood by classical scholars. Still, this contextual rule for interpretation is widely discussed in classical Fiqh literature, and is central to the thought of Ibn Taymiyya’s main student, Ibn Qayyim al-Jawziyya (d. 1350), who has devoted large chapters on it. He is also highly revered among Salafi-Wahhabi circles, and is therefore cited here by the Letter as a way to use their own authorities against them. Tariq Ramadan, *Radical reform: Islamic ethics and liberation* (Oxford: Oxford University Press, USA, 2008), 101–25. Anas bin Mohd Yunus e.a., “An Analysis of Fiqh al-Waqi` (An Understanding of Contemporary Problems) on the Ruling of Compulsory Boycott of KFC (Malaysia)”, *International Journal of Humanities and Social Science* 3, no. 1 (january 2013): 198. Al-Zuhayli, *Ibid*, 2:367-369. In general the Salafi-Wahabi reject the (classical and modernistic) rational *ijtihad* implied by *Fiqh al-Waq'i*. See: “Some thoughts on the phrase Fiqh al-waaqi’ (understanding reality)”, Islamqa, april 12, 2010, accessed juli 12, 2016, <https://islamqa.info/en/138348>. “The true meaning of Fiqh al-wāqi’”, june 13, 2007, accessed juli 12, 2016, <https://www.troid.ca/authors/scholars-the-major-scholars/84-salih-ibn-fawzan-al-fawzan/337-the-true-meaning-of-fiqh-al-waqi>.

⁹⁹ Letter, *Ibid*, 8-9. Here the Letter cites two Qur’an verses, 6:151 and 5:32, who both directly state that innocent human life is inviolable (*haram*). The Letter’s description of innocent life is those “neither combatants nor armed”, and that ISIS only killed because these innocent people rejected ISIS’ claims. This definition of ‘innocence’ and its concept of human inviolability (*haram* or *isma*) is in conformity with both classical Sunni Islam and modern international law, as stated by the Hanafi scholar al-Sarakhsi (d. 1090): “The fundamental rule is that each human is inviolable, and is only allowed to be killed if a person participates in war. When the war

7. It is forbidden in Islam to kill emissaries, ambassadors, and diplomats; hence it is forbidden to kill journalists and aid workers.¹⁰⁰

ends through a treaty, the person's life becomes inviolable again." Abu Bakr al-Sarakhsi, *al-Mabsut* (Beirut: Dar al-Marifa, 1993), 10:81. Similar statements are found across the schools, such as the Shafi'i Muhaddith Ibn al-Salah al-Shahrazuri (d. 1245): "The original ruling is preservation of unbelievers and letting them live. Because God the Exalted does not want destruction of creation and neither has he created them to be killed. Killing them is only allowed in order to neutralize their harm, not because it's a punishment for their disbelief. This world is not the place of judgement, but the place of punishment is in the Hereafter." Ibn Salih al-Shahrazuri al-Shafi'i, *Fatawa Ibn Salih* (n.p., n.dt.), 224, <http://adelabdo.yoo7.com/t6466-topic>. This is even stated by Ibn Taymiyya and his student Ibn Qayyim: "Killing is only obligatory when facing warfare and armed combat not when facing disbelief (*Kufr*). For this reason, neither women are to be killed nor children, or the elderly, nor the blind nor those worshippers who do not fight, rather we fight against those who fight us. This was the way of the Messenger of God in dealing with the people of the earth, he used to fight those who fought against him until they either entered into the religion [of Islam], make an agreement or treaty with him or came under his authority by paying the Jizya." Ibn Qayyim al-Jawziyya, *Ahkam Ahl al-Dhimma* (al-Dumam: Ramada li-lNushr, 1997), 1:110. On an extensive discussion on human inviolability in Islam, see: Recep Senturk, 'Sociology of Rights: "I Am Therefore I Have Rights": Human Rights in Islam between Universalistic and Communalistic Perspectives', *Muslim World Journal of Human Rights* 2, no. 1 (September 2005), accessed July 13, 2016, doi:10.2202/1554-4419.1030. Qur'an 5:32's statement to preserve life is generally stated as "the main principle on which the Shari'a is based." Qadi Abu Bakr Muhammad Ibn al-'Arabi, *Ahkām al-Qur'ān* (Beirut: Dār al-Kutub al-'ilmiyyah, 1996), 2:89. Al-Zuhayli, *Ibid*, 2:310-313. Both verses provide exceptions on this inviolability, "through right (*bi-lHaqq*)" and "because of murder or humanitarian corruption on earth (*bi-ghayri nafs aw fasad fi-lArdh*)", which is generally understood to refer to the allowance of capital punishment in case of murder, adultery, and apostasy, and in the case of robbery, rebellion, and aggressive warfare (as stated in the second verse 5:33). Some understood *fasad fi-lArdh* as also referring to idolatry (*Shirk*), thereby allowing the killing of non-Muslims, but this is rejected as a cause (*sabab* or 'illa) to kill someone by itself by the majority of schools. Ibn al-'Arabi, *Ibid*, 2:89-90. Nasr e.a., *The Study Quran*, 292-293, 398-399. On idolatry and unbelief as a cause of war, see fn. 101 below. The Letter avoids the discussion on any of the capital punishment here, especially on apostasy, which is a complicated issue, but vital in the way Jihadi-Salafism approaches other Muslims. See the discussion on this at point 9, fn. 102, below. Also it wouldn't surprise me if ISIS views 5:32 as abrogated by Jihad verses as 9:5/73, even though verse 5:32 was never seen as abrogated by the classical scholars. The Letter missed an important opportunity here by not discussing these verses in a more elaborate fashion, as the overwhelming majority of exegetes see verse 5:32 as foundational for universal human inviolability, and provided extensive proof of this in their commentaries. The shortcomings of the Letter here is also pointed out by Landau-Tasseron as it avoided to discuss the various interpretations. Landau-Tasseron, *Ibid*, 7.

¹⁰⁰ Letter, *Ibid*, 9. Here the Letter directly refers to the killings of journalists and aidworkers as Foley, Sotloff and Haines. According to the Letter, their professions are equal to the classical status of envoy (*rasul*). As Landau-Tasseron emphasizes: "[T]he Shari'a justification adduced in the Letter (i.e. that are comparable to envoys) is more significant, for it illustrates the feasibility of applying tolerant traditional Islamic norms to modern circumstances by inference." Landau-Tasseron, *Ibid*, 7. But even if their modern professions are not equal to classical envoy, they still were protected as *Musta'amin* (visa holders), which can be provided by any Muslim in the land. The *Aman* (security) declaration (based on Qur'an 9:6) can be given in an informal or formal fashion, by any Muslim, even if it is a slave or a Muslim enemy soldier, to any person. This *Aman* is never to be violated, except in the case of certain acts of the visa holder falls under criminal law. As stated by Bsoul: "The common *aman* and *isti'man*, one can conclude that the *musta'minin* are non-Muslims from the *harbiyyuh* (enemies in

8. Jihad in Islam is defensive war. It is not permissible without the right cause, the right purpose and without the right rules of conduct.¹⁰¹

war) who enter *dar al-Islam* temporarily under safe conduct (*aman*) for the purpose of a specific matter and without being obliged to observe the *ahkam al-Islam* or the impositions placed on *dhimmi* in general.” ISIS’ killing of the above mentioned persons were done as a form of hostage, whereby they demanded America and Britain to stop their bombings. Other foreigners were killed for similar objectives, but some were also accused of spying. In classical Islam it is forbidden to use captives as hostages, especially when they are noncombatants. Abu Bakr al-Razi al-Jassas, *Mukhtasar Ikhtilaf al-Ulama’ li-ITahawi* (Beirut: Dar al-Basha’r al-Islamiyya, 2013), 3:449 – 452. Wahba al-Zuhayli, *al-Fiqh al-Islamiyyu wa Adilatuhu* (Damascus: Dar al-Fikr, 2012), 3:731 – 737. Labeeb Ahmed Bsoul, *International Treaties (Mu’ahadat) in Islam: Theory and Practice in the Light of Islamic International Law (Siyar) according to Orthodox Schools* (United States: University Press of America, 2007), 39–106.

¹⁰¹ This subject has the longest text in the Letter and is divided in five parts: 1) Introduction to the term Jihad and its distinction into the greater (struggle against one’s ego) and lesser Jihad (struggle in war), 2) Intention behind Jihad, 3) Reason behind Jihad, 4) Goal of Jihad, and 5) Rules of conduct of Jihad. Classically, the distinction between the lesser (*al-Jihad al-Asghar*) and greater Jihad (*al-Jihad al-Akbar*) was always accepted, as the majority of the Muslim population was not involved in warfare. Only with the advent of 20th century Salafism did the authenticity-weakness of the Hadith became relevant to reject this distinction to make Jihad only equal to warfare. The Letter directly responds to this criticism by referring to Qur’an 25:52, through which the content (*matn*) of the Hadith is confirmed by a stronger text, whereby the weakness of the chain of transmission (*isnad*) becomes less problematic. Letter, *Ibid*, 12. This is an important solution to overcoming the weakness of the tradition, as the overwhelming majority of classical Qur’an commentators see chapter 25 as early Meccan and therefore could not contain any reference to Jihad as warfare. Therefore the “greater Jihad (*jihadan kabiran*)” mentioned in 25:52 could only refer to pacifist and ideological struggle, and proves the division into greater and lesser Jihad. Abū Manṣūr al-Māturīdī, *Tā’wīlāt Ahl al-Sunnah* (Beirut: Dār al-Kutub al-‘ilmiyyah, 2005), 8:3, 8:33. Nasr e.a., *The Study Quran*, 899. Concerning the intention one needs for Jihad, the Letter cites a Hadith which says that a certain person will claim to have made Jihad for the sake of God, but will be accused to lie about his real intent and then will be dragged to hell. This Hadith is used as a warning and accusation against the fighters of ISIS. The reason or cause for Jihad is according to the Letter for defense against aggression and persecution. The ‘Jihad is only defensive’ argument is not simple Islamic modernistic apologetics starting with Mahmud Shaltut, but has technically always been the dominant position among the Hanafi, Maliki and Hanbali schools. Ahmed Al-Dawoody, *The Islamic law of war: Justifications and regulations* (United Kingdom: Palgrave Macmillan, 2011), 76–81. But the modern formulation has shifted its discourse away from Fiqh terminology on the ‘rulings of war (*Ahkam al-Harb*)’ and ‘causes of war (*Asbab al-Harb*)’ to focus on why, when and how the Prophet fought his battles as the underlying context of the causes of revelation (*Asbab al-Nuzul*) behind the Qur’anic verses on war. Thereby the approach to the concept of Jihad is historicized and relativized. Mahmoud Muhammad Shaltut, *The Qur’an and Combat*, translated by Lamyia Al-Khraisha (n.p.: The Royal Islamic Strategic Studies Centre, 2013), 33–48, <http://rissc.jo/the-quran-and-combat-by-imam-mahmoud-muhammad-shaltut/>; Al-Dawoody, *Ibid*, 81-84. It is also here where we see Shaykh al-Yaqoubi’s influence on the Letter by emphasizing that only scholars from the Shafi’i school believed in aggressive warfare, as he constantly emphasizes this matter in his fatwa and other media. Tam Hussein, *The revolt of the Sheikh*, January 24, 2013, <http://www.newstatesman.com/world-affairs/world-affairs/2013/01/revolt-sheikh>. We see this also in the Letter’s opening introduction where it criticized the false combining of a Qur’anic verse (“He [Muhammad] was sent as a mercy to the worlds”) with a Hadith (“I [Muhammad] was sent with the sword”), but also emphasized that this Hadith is “specific to a certain time and place which have since expired”, thereby historicizing the Hadith in a way unprecedented in classical Islamic thought. Letter, *Ibid*, 4. The same is done to

the Hadith “I have been ordered to fight people until they say: ‘There is no god but God.’”, and combined with Qur’an 48:28 is made specific (*khass*) to a historical event. Letter, *Ibid*, 12. This historicizing is an important step, but are sadly given without proof. One of the best historicizing approaches to this Hadith and Qur’an Jihad verses as 9:5/73 is by the Tunisian mufti and reformist scholar Tahir ibn Ashur (d. 1972) who historicizes them through Qur’an 9:29 and 2:256. As all scholars accept the Jizya (polltax) is accepted from non-Muslims, it means fighting cannot be absolute. Therefore the commands to fight the unbelievers is specific (*khass*) and conditional (*muqayyad*) to the Arab pagans, while the command for non-Muslims to obtain citizenship with religious freedom through paying the Jizya is absolute (*mutlaq*) in application.. Tahir Ibn ‘Ashur, *Tafsir al-Tahrir wa al-Tanwir*, (Tunis: Dar Sahnun lil-Nushr walTawziy‘a, n.dt.), 3:25-28, 301. See also below at fn. 106. In this way these war-aggressive Hadith and Qur’an verses are made specific and do not provide absolute goals which need to be pursued. Although the classical tradition has always viewed these verses and traditions through historical lenses, this didn’t make them limited to that historical event only. The Letter’s strongest arguments concern the rules of conduct pertaining to war as there was a strong consensus (*ijma’*) on these matters in the classical tradition. Non-combatants are not to be harmed, and it is this subject which is repeated constantly throughout Tafsir and Fiqh texts concerning war. Such as summarized by the Shafi’i scholar ‘Abd Allah al-Baydawi (d. 1286) in his exegesis on Qur’an verse 2:190 “[Fight the unbelievers] without them being from the elderly and the young and the monks and women or all of the unbelievers that desist fighting the Muslims and its purpose.” Abd Allāh al-Baydawi, *Anwār al-Tanzīl wa āsrār al-Tā’wīl*, (Beirut: Dār Sādr, 2004), 1:114. For more on this, see: Akgündüz, *Ibid*, 634-635. Tahir-ul-Qadri, *Ibid*, 117-139. Majid Khadduri, *The Islamic law of nations: Shaybānī’s Siyar* (Baltimore: The Johns Hopkins University Press, 2001), 91–92. Wahba al-Zuhayli, *Al-Fiqh Al-Islamiyyu Wa Adilatuhu*, 3:720 – 721. Al-Dawoody, *Ibid*, 111-119. Tahir-ul-Qadri, *Ibid*, 57-156. Ahmad b. Abu Said b. ‘Ubaydullah Mullājīyūn al-Ḥanafī, *Tafsīrāt al-Aḥmadiyya fī Bayān al-Ayāt al-Shar’iyyah* (Beirut: Dār al-Kutub al-‘ilmiyyah, 2010), 86–87. Asma Afsaruddin, “Recovering the Early Semantic Purview of Jihad and Martyrdom: Challenging Statist-Military Perspectives”, in *Crescent and dove: Peace and conflict resolution in Islam*, edited by Qamar-ul Huda (Washington, D.C.: United States Institute of Peace Press, 2010), 39–62. The way the Letter portrays Jihad is very similar to how al-Azhar portrays it: Dar al-ifta al-Misriyya, “Jihad: Concept, history and contemporary application”, accessed juli 14, 2016, <http://eng.dar-alifta.org/foreign/ViewArticle.aspx?ID=78>. The Letter ends this subject with a discussion on how to deal with prisoners of war. It claims killing prisoners of war is forbidden in Islam, and that the Prophet only killed war criminals. Only with this exception is the political leader of the Muslims (the *imam*) allowed to order the killing of prisoners. Here the Letter promotes a minority position in Islamic law, also it doesn’t discuss the important distinction between Muslim and non-Muslim prisoners. The classical discussion centered around Qur’an verses 47:4 (which orders to overtake the unbelieving enemy to take them prisoner whom after the war must be ransomed or released) and 8:67-71 (which rejects letting prisoners live until the war is over), if these verses could be reconciled, are specific, or that they abrogate each other. In general there is a consensus, based on 47:4 and 49:9-10, that Muslim prisoners (in the case of intra-Muslim war) are never to be killed, but to be released after the war. The main disagreement is on the treatment of non-Muslim prisoners. The minority position, mainly held by Hanafi scholars, holds that no prisoners may be killed, but must be ransomed or released freely. The ransoming could be done through ransom by their leadership or family, by accepting the Jizya, or by accepting to become slaves with the possibility of buying their freedom after a period of time. As stated by the Hanafi scholar Mahmud al-Alusi (d. 1854): “Killing is forbidden after taking captive and this is said by al-Hassan [al-Basri]. And this is taken from Ibn Jarir [al-Tabari]. And Ibn Mardawiyya on that he said: When pilgrims arrived with prisoners and brought towards Ibn Umar (ra) a man was killed and Ibn Umar said: “Weren't we on this commanded by God most High saying: {When you have overrun them, bind the captives firmly. Thereafter either release them or take ransom.} And in this is the ruling (*Hukm*) on captives.[...] And I infer also in the verse is [...] that God the Most High determines goodness between release or ransom, and is the clear apparent reading (*al-Zāhar*), that the underlying intention in releasing is the letting go for free, and the intention of releasing them through the omission of killing and the preservation of their necks, or they relinquish by accepting the payment of the Jizya (poll tax) and thus they become protected minorities (*Ahl al- Dhimmah*).” Mahmud al-Alusi, *Ruh al-*

Ma'ani fi tafsir al-Qur'an al-'Azim (Beirut: Dar al- Kutub al-'ilmiyya, 1995), 13:196 – 198. The majority position is that the Muslim leader (*imam*) can choose, based on general welfare (*maslaha*), between releasing, ransoming, enslaving, and killing. The position of the Letter would have been stronger if it had emphasized that Muslim prisoners (which are the majority of ISIS captives) are never to be killed based on juristic consensus (*ijma'*), and that there can be no juristic retaliation (*qisas*) if they have killed non-combatants through bombings (as ISIS killed many Muslim soldiers and fighter pilots with the reason these enemy soldiers killed Muslim families through shelling and bombing), as penal laws (*hudud*) are not applied in warfare. Al-Zuhayli, *Al-Fiqh Al-Islamiyyu*, 3:679-776. Akgündüz, *Ibid*, 637-638. Khadduri, *Ibid*, 100-102. Abd Allah b. Hassan b. Mahmud Hafiz al-Din al-Nasafi, *Tafsir al-Nasafi 'aw Mudarak al-Tanzil wa Haqa'iq al- Ta'wil* (Cairo: al-Maktaba al-Tawfiqiyya, z.d.), 4:183. Abu Bakr al-Razi al-Jassas, *Ahkām al-Qur'an* (Beirut: Dār ihyā' al-Turāth al-'Arabiyya, 1985), 5:271. Wahba al-Zuhayli, *al-Tafsir al-Munir fi al-'Aqidah wa al-Sharī'ah wa al-Minhaj* (Damascus: Dār al-Fikr al-Mu'asir, 1998), 26:89-91. Abu Abd Allah Muhammad al-Ansari al-Qurtubi, *Mukhtasar Tafsir al-Qurtubi* (Beirut: Dar al-Kutub al-'ilmiyyah, 2001), 1:212. Landau-Tasseron makes several claims in her review, pointing out the importance and the shortcomings of the Letter's historicizing turn, but also other ones which are academically troublesome: 1) She claims classical Sunnism dominantly believed in offensive Jihad, while, as discussed above, this is not true. The abrogation of peaceful or war-ethical verses by 9:5 was understood also by many classical scholars as being a specific abrogation (*naskh al-Khass*) of an unconditional rule (*mutlaq*) to which it returns to after the specific situation is over. 2) She ignores the important distinction between the three major approaches exegetes had towards the term *Fitna*, which, especially the Hanafi, dominantly understood as “the expulsion from one's homes and land” as they saw the conjunction *wa* with the preceding sentence as a expository cause (*al-Hal*) of *Fitna* which determines its meaning (*tufid al-Ma'ana*). One opinion cited by al-Nasafi is even more telling: “When people ask, ‘What is worse than death (*al-Mawt*)?’”, he said: ‘Someone who desires in [some situation] death (*yatamannā fhi al-Mawt*).’ Therefore this makes the expulsion from the homeland (*al-'ikhrāj min al-Watan*) from the *Fitna* which makes someone desire death.” Al-Nasafi, *Ibid*, 1:119. And when the classical commentators did understand it as *Shirk*, it was because they linked it to the specific *Shirk* performed by the *Ahl Makka* at the holy ritual area (*al-Masjid al-Haram*) surrounding the Ka'aba (and therefore not polytheism in general), or because the *Ahl Makka*, because of their oppressive unbelief, forced the Muslims to fight in the holy month, expelled them from their homes, forced them to renounce Islam, and withheld them from performing the pilgrimage, which all together is called a great *Fitna* in Qur'an 2:217. In this way their *Shirk* is seen as the cause (*al-'illa*) for the oppression (*zulm*) of the Muslims, and must be fought because of this. As stated above, the majority of scholars clearly stated that the *Shirk* or *Kufr* of others is not a cause of war (*sabab al-Harb*) by itself, and therefore must be taken together with their commentaries on verses such these. 3) She states that protected non-Muslim minorities were expected to convert eventually, while the fact is that classical scholars expected religious pluralism to be present until the end of times as pluralism is stated clearly to be God's will by Qur'an verses 2:213, 5:48, 10:19, 11:117-119, 16:93, etc. Therefore the logical expectation that people convert to, in the eyes of Muslim scholars, to the more rational religion of Islam, must be separated from the idea that this entailed an expectation of the conversion of the totality of humanity. 4) Although she correctly mentions there were two opinions pertaining to prisoners, she fails to distinguish between Muslim and non-Muslim captivity rulings, as discussed above. Al-Māturīdī, *Ibid*, 2:65-67. Ibn al-'Arabi, *Ibid*, 1:154. Al-Jassas, *Ibid*, 1:314. Al-Baydawi, *Ibid*, 1:114, 122-123. Nasr, *The Study Qur'an*, 83-85, 492. Abu al-Layth al-Samarqandi, *Tafsir al-Samarqandi aw Bahr al-'Ulum* (Beirut: Dar al-Kutub al-'Ilmiyya, 1993), 1:179. Landau-Tasseron, *Ibid*, 7-9. Landau-Tasseron also criticizes the Letter's discussion on the false combination of mercy and sword by invoking another Hadith herself which states that Muhammad was pleased to see people forcibly dragged into paradise, meaning they were forced to convert. This explanation is tedious to use as a general explanation, and is also not the explanation provided by Friedmann who discusses it in relation to the historical Arab pagans, and not non-Muslims in general. And the variations of this Hadith (which are of varying degrees of authenticity, an element not discussed by Friedmann) has been understood by the majority of classical scholars as referring to: 1) Unbelievers taken captive who converted later on willingly after their good treatment by Muslims during their captivity, 2) non-Muslim captives dragged into

9. It is forbidden in Islam to declare people non-Muslim unless he (or she) openly declares disbelief.¹⁰²

Muslim ruled territory (*Dar al-Islam*), 3) Muslims taken captive and who died during their captivity. As Friedmann states, forced conversion is rarely discussed in relation to these traditions. Mulla Ali al-Qari, *Mirqat al-Mafatih Sharh Mishkat al-Masabih* (Beirut: Dar al-Fikr, 2002), 6:2046. “Dragged into Jannah in chains.”, June 23, 2015, accessed July 13, 2016, <http://hadithanswers.com/dragged-into-jannah-in-chains/>. Yohanan Friedmann, *Tolerance and coercion in Islam: Interfaith relations in the Muslim tradition* (United Kingdom: Cambridge University Press, 2003), 118–120. Landau-Tasseron, *Ibid*, 5.

¹⁰² Letter, *Ibid*, 14-16. This is the second largest subject discussed in the Letter. In classical Sunnism, declaring someone an apostate (*murtad*) through excommunication (*takfir*) is an exception, and in general is viewed as treason against the state and not just a foregoing or violation of one’s faith. Which is also why the Hanafi school rejected capital punishment for female apostates. In Jihadi-Salafism, apostasy is easily acquired due to the long list of *Nawaqid al-Islam*, as discussed in fn. 90, and is used to coerce the non-combatant Sunni population under their control into compliance, and excommunicate opponents (such as al-Qaeda’s *Jahbat al-Nusra*) and critics (such as many of the Letter’s signatories who were declared apostates in ISIS’ *Dabiq* magazine). Also classically one could declare a certain action or statement by a Muslim to be *Kufr*, but this wouldn’t directly declare that person an unbeliever. Generally, only a knowing and persistent continuation of that *Kufr* could make one an apostate, if the person is brought towards a judge. Only certain acts generated immediate apostasy, such as blasphemy towards God or the Prophet (*sibb al-Nabi*), repeated in front of a judge, would directly nullify one’s testimony of faith. Therefore the Letter correctly criticizes the behaviour of many ISIS soldiers who harass and even kill local population when they can’t answer their question pertaining to Islamic beliefs, obligations or texts. The Letter takes a wide inclusive position which accepts any declarer of the *Shahada* to be Muslim without question, which is a pre-Ghazali position in Sunnism. Although the label *Ahl al-Sunna* emerged early on, the definition of who is a Muslim was defined by being a *Shahada*-declarer and belonging to the *Ahl al-Qibla* (the people who pray towards Mecca) and is still used in later creedal works (such as the 14th century *‘Aqa’id al-Nasafi*). Not belonging to the *Ahl al-Sunna* makes one a heretic, but not directly an unbeliever. Due to the ideological threat of the Ismaili in the 11th century, this inclusivism was narrowed. Frank Griffel, “Toleration and Exclusion: Al-Shafi’i and al-Ghazali on the Treatment of Apostates”, *Bulletin of the School of Oriental and African Studies* 64, no. 03 (October 2001), doi:10.1017/s0041977x01000192. Many Jihadi-Salafi declarations cite the early works of Ibn Taymiyya, especially from his collected fatwa’s, where Ibn Taymiyya takes harsher stances compared to his later years. The Letter correctly points out that Salafism misrepresents him, and cites one of the most important citations in the whole Letter: Al-Dhahabi (d. 1348), one of his students, says: “At the end of his life, our teacher Ibn Taymiyya said: ‘I declare no one of this Umma to be an unbeliever.’” Shams al-Din al-Dhahabi, *Siyar ‘Alam al-Nabula* (Cairo: Dar al-Hadith, 2006), 11:393. It is also here where the Letter makes a surprising declaration, which although is part of classical Sunni theology, is normally not discussed in texts meant for such a wide audience due to the complicated theological postulates behind it: A Muslim can perform or believe in a subtle/hidden *Shirk* without becoming an unbeliever. A common example given in classical Sunnism is the belief that one performs acts through their own power (*quwwa*) instead of God’s, a theological claim made by the Mu’tazila, but which can be subtly believed by any Muslim, and does not make one an unbeliever but only an innovator/heretic (*mubtadi’*). Mulla Ali al-Qari, *Ibid*, 7:2878. But there are also less hidden forms of *Shirk* which can be performed by a believer (through ignorance (*jahl*), sinful attitude (*fisq*), or heretical beliefs (*bida’*)), and belong to the major sins (*al-Kaba’ir*), for which he will be temporarily punished in hell by God, but which will not make him an unbeliever. Although classical Sunnism differed on the number of major sins (7, 9, 17, or 70), they all agree on the first three (based on a Hadith in Bukhari and Muslim): *Shirk*, sorcery (*sihr*), and murder. To believe God literally sits on the throne and has literal limbs (thereby believing God has dimensions) is also a form of *Shirk*, which is an anthropomorphism (*jismiyya*) promoted by the Salafi-

10. It is forbidden in Islam to harm or mistreat—in any way—Christians or any
‘People of the Scripture’.¹⁰³

Wahhabi. This is also the reason why many Sunni scholars and institutions as al-Azhar refuse to excommunicate terrorists as unbelievers, instead they deem them as heretics and evil sinners. Al-Mazidi, Ed., *Shuruh wa Hawashi al-'Aqa'id al-Nasafiyya*, 4:423-433. Ibn Abi al-'Izz, *Ibid*, 235-237, 325-329. As the Letter mentions, ISIS distributed the book '*Kitab al-Tawhid*', by Wahhabi founder Ibn Abd al-Wahhab (d. 1792), which is a text mainly concerned with beliefs and actions which al-Wahhab viewed as *Kufr* (while classical Sunni Islam allowed them, or viewed them only as sinful. The main point of contention is on mediation of between the God and the living through the deceased (*tawasul*)). The discussion on *takfir* is therefore directly related to Wahhabism. On Wahhabism, see: Zubair Qamar, "Wahhabism: Understanding the Roots and Role Models of Islamic Extremism", 1994, <http://www.sunnah.org/articles/Wahhabiarticleedit.htm>. On apostasy and its punishment, see: Abdullah Saeed, "Pre-Modern Islamic Legal Restrictions on Freedom of Religion, with Particular Reference to Apostasy and its Punishment", in *Islamic Law and International Human Rights Law*, edited by Mark S. Ellis, Anver M. Emon, and Benjamin Glahn (United Kingdom: Oxford University Press, 2012), 226–46. Akgündüz, *Ibid*, 370-376. Taha Jabir Alalwani, *Apostasy in Islam: A historical and scriptural analysis* (London: International Institute of Islamic Thought, 2011). Nasr, *The Study Quran*, 94-95. Moataz Ahmed El Fegiery, "Islamic law and freedom of religion: The case of Apostasy and its legal implications in Egypt", *Muslim World Journal of Human Rights* 10, no. 1 (januari 10, 2013), doi:10.1515/mwjhr-2012-0007. On the *takfir* on Jabhat al-Nusra: "ISIS statement asking all militants to declare, without hesitation, Takfeer (apostasy) on Jabhat al-nusra (AQ)", juli 13, 2016, accessed juli 13, 2016, <http://syria.liveuamap.com/en/2016/8-june-isis-statement-asking-all-militants-to-declare-without>. On the *takfir* on mainstream Sunni scholars: "ISIS releases Apostasy hit list of 21 western Muslim leaders", *Foreign Policy*, april 14, 2016, accessed juli 14, 2016, <http://dailycaller.com/2016/04/14/isis-releases-apostasy-hit-list-of-21-western-muslim-leaders/>.

¹⁰³ Letter, *Ibid*, 17-18. Here the Letter makes three main arguments: 1) Arab Christians are co-citizens since the dawn of Islam, and fall under ancient agreements of protection. 2) Their treatment is based on kindness and justice as stated in Qur'an 60:8. 3) The Jizya is in two forms: I. Jizya as compensation for warfare as stated in Qur'an 9:29 (war-Jizya), II. Jizya as non-Muslim *Zakat* (citizen-Jizya). As Landau-Tasseront mentions, argument I is correct from a classical point of view, but fails to respond correctly to the claim made by ISIS that these treaties have been violated by the Arab Christians. According to ISIS the Arab-Christian population violated their treaties by cooperating with the Americans and Shi'a in Iraq, and with the Assad regime in Syria. According to classical Islamic law, treaties can be revoked in the case of violations such as treason (as was done by the Banu Qurayza and the Quraysh, as stated in Qur'an 9:7 and 8:58) or because Muslims want to revoke the treaty before its expire date (which is generally ten years based on the Hudaibiya treaty) because they can't fulfill it or there is a change in circumstances whereby the treaty goes against both parties' interests. With the Ottoman Tanzimat, these treaties were collapsed into equal citizenship together with Muslim citizenship in 1856. Thereby non-Muslims could only violate their modern form of citizenship (a concept which ISIS rejects), and not any treaty, so ISIS could only claim a reinstatement of the *Aqd al-Dhimma* and not a violation of one. Also as the Arab-Christians are mixed with the Muslim population and do not form a separate community that could form their own army, technically no violation could occur. Landau-Tasseront claims that the Letter's Jizya binary distinction is a modern one and doesn't exist in classical commentaries. Technically this is not correct as classical Tafsir and Fiqh literature discuss Jizya as a form of *al-Dara'ib*, taxes, as it does with *Zakat* (alms-tax) and *Kharaj* (land-tax). And pre-modern scholars as Isma'il Haqqi al-Burusawi (d. 1715) explain the war-Jizya as a reprimand (*zajr*) for the performed act of war. What is mainly discussed in commentaries on 9:29 is how non-Muslims become *Ahl al-Dhimma*, and from whom it is to be asked (for example, it is only asked from non-Muslim males who are not poor (*faqir*)). But non-Muslims also became *Ahl al-Dhimma* through self-engaged treaties without Muslims conquering them. The majority of scholars (especially from the Hanafi and Maliki),

reject the concept that the Jizya is a punishment ('*aquba*) for non-Muslim *Kufr* (*la yajuz an yakun akhdh al-Jizya minhum radda bi-kufrhum*). Also it is not a debt, and when a person is unable to pay it for one year, he becomes a receiver of *Zakat* from the Muslim treasury (*bayt al-Mal*). It is not asked from women, children, sick, old, clergy, and the poor. It is therefore also not a polltax for being a potential male combatants as non-Muslim male poor could join enemy armies. One of the repeated notions is that it is a sign of acceptance (*maqbul*) of the treaty ('*ahd*) with the Muslim state, and the subjugation (*dhil*) to Shari'a governance. But in all, the Jizya did mirror the *Zakat* levied from Muslims, not always in amount, but in who received (poor, sick, and elderly) and who payed (those with wealth, with the difference that *Zakat* is levied from male and female). Both the war-Jizya and the citizenship-Jizya provide the same *dhimmi* rights (right to freedom of religion and movement, family, livelihood, trade, and protection of life, property, honor etc.), and restrictions (many of these restrictions were not or rarely upheld by Muslim rulers, nor was a general agreement among classical scholars about these restrictions as they were not based on Islamic sources, but they included: no building of new places of worship (which is the most ignored restriction of all, there was even an increase of churches being build in Syria and Egypt because Christian sects, normally suppressed by Byzantine Orthodoxy, were now allowed to build churches and worship freely), clothing guidelines (based on Persian influences), and restrictions on holding military and political positions (throughout Muslim history there were generals and viziers of Jewish, Christian, and Zoroastrian origins)). The schools also differed on the equal or unequal judicial treatment of non-Muslims and Muslims. The Hanafi and several Maliki understood the Qur'anic calls for justice to mean equal treatment of Muslims and non-Muslims in punishments, compensation, and in being witnesses. The Shafi'i generally understood the application of justice to mean equal treatment within the socio-religious classes, but not between them. Not all people became *Ahl al-Dhimma* through war, as Muslims took control over many territories through treaties. Therefore Qur'an 9:29 has not been the cause for all forms of Jizya-treaties, and is the distinction between war-Jizya and citizenship-Jizya not a complete modernistic construct. Modern citizenship is both a negation of classical faith discrimination, and a collapse of the rights and duties (*Ahl al-Dhimma* lost discriminating laws and obstacles, and Muslims got the freedom to apostatize) of both sides of that discrimination, into a singular concept of citizenship, which maintains similar characteristics (*sifat*) in rights as classical '*Aqd al-Dhimma* (treaty of protection) constructs, and is therefore according to the majority of modern scholars acceptable from a Shari'a perspective. Many Muslim countries still apply classical family law, thereby still discriminate based on religion in marriage, inheritance, and divorce, and still have societal discrimination of non-Muslims, and judicial restrictions on freedom of Muslims to apostasy and heresy (generally prosecuted for violation of public order or blasphemy instead of apostasy), but slowly many countries are reforming their family law (such as Jordan) and a general reform of Muslim constitutionalism has been called upon by the Marrakesh Declaration (discussed below). The destruction of churches (forbidden by Qur'an 22:40, and by juristic consensus), and the harassment of Christians by ISIS is a violation of the classical rights provided in the '*Aqd al-Dhimma*. But as ISIS also ignores classical consensus on war ethics and prisoners, it is not surprising that their 'reintroduction' of the Jizya ignores classical precepts on this as well, or emphasizes certain precepts that were normally ignored. ISIS doesn't want to reintroduce classical Shari'a governance, but to construct one of its own which reflects the brutality of the dictatorships plaguing that region for half a century, and the chaos viewed to be correspondent to their eschatological ideas. Landau-Tasserou, *Ibid*, 11. Bsoul, *Ibid*, 52-67, 132-136. Emon, *Religious pluralism and Islamic law*, 97-105. Joseph Schacht, *An introduction to Islamic law* (New York: Oxford University Press, 1982), 130-133. Al-Zuhayli, *Al-Fiqh Al-Islamiyyu*, 3:742-752. Akgündüz, *Ibid*, 84-94. Khadduri, *Ibid*, 100-102. Tahir-ul-Qadri, *Ibid*, 157-168. A. R. I. Doi, *Non-Muslims under Shari'ah (Islamic law)* (Kuala Lumpur: A.S. Noorden, 1979), 22-118. Ahmed Abu Bakr al-Khassaf, *Adab Al-Qadi* (New Delhi: Adam Publishers, 2010), 93. Al-Alusi, *Ibid*, 9:373-375. Muhammad Thana Allah al-Mazhari, *al-Tafsir al-Mazhari* (Beirut: Dar al-Kutub al-'Ilmiyya, 2007), 3:265 - 275. Isma'il Haqqi al-Burusawi, *Ruh al-Bayan fi Tafsir al-Qur'an* (Beirut: Dar al-Kutub al-'Ilmiyya, 2013), 3:433 - 434. Robert G. Hoyland, *In God's path: The Arab Conquests and the Creation of an Islamic Empire* (United Kingdom: Oxford University Press, 2015), 55-57. John A Morrow, *The Covenants of the Prophet Muhammad with the Christians of the World* (United States: Angelico Press, 2013). On ISIS

11. It is obligatory to consider Yazidis as People of the Scripture.¹⁰⁴

12. The re-introduction of slavery is forbidden in Islam. It was abolished by universal consensus.¹⁰⁵

eschatology, see: Graeme Wood, *What ISIS really wants*, (The Atlantic), april 14, 2016, <http://www.theatlantic.com/magazine/archive/2015/03/what-isis-really-wants/384980/>.

¹⁰⁴ Letter, *Ibid*, 18. Here the Letter correctly states that the majority of classical scholars (again especially the Hanafi and Maliki), saw every non-Muslim as acceptable for a treaty and therefore also the *'Aqd al-Dhimma*. Only the Meccan Quraysh pagans were exempted from this, which after the first Islamic century has become a redundant ruling (see also below at fn. 106). Although the Letter previously confessed truthfully that it is the Shafi'i school that expounded aggressive Jihad, on this subject ignores it, even though it is again vital for it to be discussed as ISIS has clearly stated that they follow the Shafi'i on this issue. In general the Shafi'i only accepted Christians and Jews as *Ahl al-Kitab* and as *Ahl al-Dhimma*. The Hanafi and Maliki differentiated between *Ahl al-Kitab*, who's food could be eaten and women could be married, and the *Ahl al-Dhimma* which included all non-Muslims (Christians, Jews, Zoroastrians, Sabians, Buddhists, Hindus, Brahman, pagans, non-religious philosophers, atheists etc.). In Islamic law, precedence and welfare determine the application of public law, and the Hanafi and Maliki position has always been applied, even if the rulers followed the Shafi'i school of law. Therefore, historically, has the Shafi'i position never been applied in Muslim history. ISIS' deliberate rejection of this precedence is probably directly connected to their desire to reinstate slavery, for which they needed a community to enslave. Although the Yazidi have been persecuted several times over the centuries by Muslim rulers, it was always been justified as being caused by rebellion or breach of treaty. Some scholars (which also some ISIS supporters have cited) have viewed them as apostates or heretics due to their worship of a 12th century Muslim Sufi, but the general view has always been that they belong to the category of Sabians or Zoroastrians. Their lack of written scripture has only been an issue for their status as *Ahl al-Kitab* (people of the Book, i.e. if they are Sabian or not), but not for being deemed *Ahl al-Dhimma* (they are generally viewed as equal to Zoroastrians) as this has no requirements. Al-Alusi, *Ibid*. Al-Mazhari, *Ibid*. Al-Baydawi, *Ibid*, 1: 402-403. Tahir Ibn Ashur, *Ibid*, 5:162-164. Bsoul, *Ibid*. Z. Khenchelaoui and J. Burrell, "The Yezidis, people of the spoken word in the midst of people of the book", *Diogenes* 47, no. 187 (september 1, 1999), doi:10.1177/039219219904718703. United Nations Human Rights Council, *Report of the Independent International Commission of Inquiry on the Syrian Arab Republic: "They came to destroy": ISIS Crimes Against the Yazidis*, (n.p., 2016), http://www.ohchr.org/Documents/HRBodies/HRCouncil/CoISyria/A_HRC_32_CRP.2_en.pdf.

¹⁰⁵ Letter, *Ibid*, 18-19. It is here where the Letter introduces its' most modernistic and reformist opinion of all. Their argument is: 1) "No scholar of Islam disputes that one of the Islam's aims (*ahdaf al-Islam*) is to abolish slavery." 2) Several Qur'an verses and the Sunna show that ending slavery is desired. 3) The Prophet supported non-revelatory treaties that expounded rational-ethical values. 4) Slavery was abolished through consensus of the Umma (*ijma' al-Muslimun*) and worldly consensus (*ijma' al-'Alam*). 5) Abolishment of slavery is a "milestone in human history (lit. great virtue in human history (*fadil kabir fi tarikh al-Insaniya*)). 6) After a century of Muslim consensus ISIS violated this and revived a *Fitna*, corruption on earth (*fasad fi-lArdh*), and lewdness (*fahisha*) which the Shari'a tried to undo, and is *Haram* according to consensus. 7) Muslim countries are signatories of anti-slavery conventions. 8) This can cause lash-back against Muslims in general (i.e. Islamophobia). Landau-Tasserion correctly criticizes the claim that the Shari'a, as in the 1200 year development of Sunni Fiqh, has collectively sought to abolish slavery. As the Shari'a both represent the sources (*nusus*, i.e. Qur'an and Sunna) and its accumulated interpretation tradition (*furu' al-Fiqh*), it certainly can be claimed that the Shari'a *nusus* desire to minimize and decrease slavery. The *nusus* never state abolishment as the final aim,

nor contain a text that demands the continuation of slavery, therefore this interpretation can not simply be claimed as farfetched or a modern projection on the text, as there is no text discussing the making of slaves, only the emancipation of slaves (although there is a discussion on making war captives into slaves, which is not directly stated in the Qur'anic text, but was seen as a humanitarian option to avoid killing prisoners of war, see fn. 101 above). The only problem with a *Sola Scriptura* approach on this issue as being representative of Sunni Islam is, that in 1200 years of Fiqh, only a handful of scholars have clearly stated that slavery should be forbidden (*haram*), or deemed it as disliked (*makruh*), due to it being unethical and/or because it was a practice inherited from pre-Islamic times (*athar al-Kufr*). The majority of classical scholars accepted slaves through inheritance and through taking captives of war, as based on the Sunna. These two slave-making options were a severe reduction of the slave-making options available in pre-Islamic times. Due to the cultural centrality of slavery in the medieval world, several classical scholars claimed Jihad must be made every year to replenish the amount of slaves. Slave-making was therefore discussed in Fiqh texts in the chapters on Jihad and spoils of war, and had no separate chapters on slave-making existed, instead they do contain separate chapters on the manumission of slaves. There was a consensus on it being forbidden to enslave *Ahl al-Dhimma*, as they have a legal rights-status in the *Dar al-Islam*. Which is why counting the Yazidi as *Ahl al-Dhimma* is of importance. The rulings concerning captured women and turning them into slaves differ immensely and are generally based on the personal reasoning (*ijtihad*) of founding scholars. Minority opinions understood Qur'an 24:33 as not referring to simple manumission of the slavegirl, but to freeing and marrying her, as they believed sex was only legal with a marriage contract. But the majority believed sex with a concubine was allowed, as the price paid for the slave was similar to the dowry paid to the wife; both bought one the right to a female's sexuality (*budu*). Qur'an 24:33 was clear that prostituting one's slaves was forbidden, but coercion to lay with one's own slaves was a grey area in classical Islam. Many classical scholars viewed coercion as morally wrong, but not as legally forbidden. Some viewed (based on a Hadith) that rape by one's owner would immediately set her free, and if raped by a stranger the latter would be punished for adultery (*Zina*). Also a slave could not be taken as a concubine if she is married (before or after her enslavement). But all the schools agreed on the good treatment of slaves, the obligation to feed and dress them, to not separate families, to not overburden them, and to always provide ways for the slaves to buy their own freedom (as is obligated by Qur'an 24:33). Almost none of the classical condemnations of slavery were linked to the Qur'anic text, but to theological-ethical arguments. One of the few clear cut condemnations of slavery (but without declaring it forbidden) by pre-modern Qur'an commentaries is by the Hanafi scholar Mahmud Hafiz al-Din al-Nasafi (d. 1312) who ingeniously says on Qur'an 4:92, where erroneous manslaughter of a fellow believer can be compensated by freeing a slave: "{and the freeing of a slave/burdened neck (*raqabah*)}...the liberation (*al-tahrir*): the emancipation, and the free and the noble emancipated thus meaning the liberated and also that the inequity in the slaves [itself is shown], and from it [equally] the nobility of the emancipation of the bird and the horse [is shown]. And the neck: [this means] the persons [bound by the neck] and it expresses about it through the ownership (*al-rā's*) in their statement: (And so in order to possess (*yumlik*) such ownership (*rā'sā*) from the necks). {believer} it is said: concerning ousting a believing person from all of the living [i.e. killing someone (*al-ā'hyā'*)] it would be necessary that a same person enters the free completely, because his release from the bindings of slavery is as bringing him back to life (*itlāqhā min qād al-riqq ka-ihyā'hā*) from which follows that the slaves are adjacent to being dead (*al-raqiq muhlaq bi-alā'mwāt*), because slavery is a leftover from the traces of Unbelief (*'āthār al-kufr*) and unbelief is a death sentence." Al-Nasafi, *Tafsir al-Nasafi*, 1:281-282. Other condemnations are mainly by theologians (*mutakalimun*) such as the Mu'tazilite Abd al-Jabbar (d. 1025) who saw slavery as rational-ethically evil (*qabih*) as every human is born with the same ethical status and obligation of which slavery is a violation of that status and an obstacle to fulfilling that obligation. A similar concept can be seen among Hanafi *Usuli* scholars such as Abu Bakr al-Sarakhsi (d. 1090): "As God the Exalted created humanity to carry His trusts, He dignified them with reason and sacred inviolability in order to be responsible for the duties and rights of Allah placed over them. Then He granted them sanctity, freedom, and property rights for them to continue carrying out their trusts. Hence, this freedom, sanctity, and right of property are granted to a person at the time they are born. Those capable of discernment and those who are not are equal in this regard, so likewise sacred

inviolability is established at birth whether they are of sound mind or not.” Abu Bakr al-Sarakhsi, *Usul al-Sarakhsi* (Beirut: Dar al-Marifa, n.d.), 2:334. The human ontology presented here sees every human as having an inherent inviolability (*'isma*), protected-to-rights-status (*dhimma*) and dignity (*akram*), which demands that a person is free from slavery. This human ontology is repeated and expanded upon throughout the Hanafi school (and taken over by *Usuli* scholars from other schools and expressed in their construction of the *Maqasid al-Shari'a*). For a discussion on this, see: Recep Senturk, “Human Rights in Islamic Jurisprudence: Why Should All Human Beings Be Inviolable?”, in *The Future of Religious Freedom: Global Challenges*, bewerkt door Allen D. Hertzke (New York: Oxford University Press, 2013). Ahmad Al-Raysuni, *Imam Al-Shatibi's Theory of the Higher Objectives and Intents of Islamic Law*, trans. Nancy Roberts (United Kingdom: International Institute of Islamic Thought, 2005), 231 – 250. Although these scholars did not directly call for the abolishment of slavery, and many times discussed the rulings on slave trade, and conduct towards to and of slaves, in their Fiqh works, it is clear that they constructed many foundational concepts on human ontology (Natural Law ethics) which are similar to those which laid the ground for the anti-slavery thought in Enlightenment-Christianity. It is these foundations that should be called upon by Muslim scholars to ground the abolishment of slavery into Islamic law. But as these are rational *Usuli* concepts, the Letter seemingly only focuses on scriptural proofs and agreed upon juristic sources as consensus. The Letter also neglects to point out that it was under the Ottoman caliph that slavery was abolished in 1848 during the Tanzimat reforms, similar to the abolishment of the Jizya. And can therefore be claimed as abolished through *Siyasa al-Shari'a* (Shari'a acknowledged political policies), a Fiqh methodology acknowledged by ISIS. Landau-Tasserion claims that the Letter's ‘worldly consensus’ argument is not a Shari'a argument, which again is an incorrect statement. The Letter first of all claimed that there is a modern, century old, consensus among the Muslim community, and that all modern scholars agree on abolishing to be a Shari'a aim. The idea of community consensus (*ijma' al-Umma*) is the original form of consensus as understood to belong to the four sources of Fiqh (Qur'an, Sunna, analogy (*Qiyas*), and consensus (*Ijma'*)). Only after the third century Hijra was it limited to the consensus of the scholars, as a full community consensus was considered impossible to determine, and the scholars were seen as representatives of the community. And even the scholarly consensus in general only represented a dominant trend, as only on a few subjects is there a full consensus. A minority view accepted the abrogation of Qur'anic and Sunna rulings through consensus based on Qur'an 4:115 which places the Messenger (i.e. source of Qur'an and Sunna) and the ‘path of the believers (i.e. community consensus) on seemingly equal footing. The majority rejected this, but differed on if one consensus could abrogate another or not. So the question here is if the continuation of slavery is based on consensus. The pro-abolishment side has four main proofs: 1) The Qur'an only discusses emancipation and not slave-making. 2) The Sunna mentions the making and trading of slaves during the Prophet's lifetime (as used by ISIS), but he freed all of his slaves at the end of his life, thereby making emancipation the dominant and abrogating Sunna. Also many Prophetic companions condemned slavery (such as the famous statement by Umar al-Khatib (d. 644): “You buy those who were born free?”). 3) Slavery is not part of the five pillars of Islam or the six pillars of faith. Nor is it a cause (*sabab*) of Jihad, only its possible byproduct. 4) It is unethical, goes against international law (which Muslim countries have signed treaties on), it is not possible in today's economy, would deter the evangelization (*dawa'*) of non-Muslims, and increases Islamophobia. The ‘worldly consensus (*ijma' al-'Alam*)’ argument has been used by al-Azhar before, and has been expanded upon by Shaykh Muhammad al-Yaqoubi in his anti-ISIS fatwa. Worldly consensus is not a modern concept in Islamic law, as many classical *Usuli* texts discuss foundational ethics (e.g. the wrongness of murder) and beliefs (e.g. belief in a creator-god) which are known through reason (i.e. Natural Law), and are therefore agreed upon by every culture around the world (typically designated as universal consensus (*ijma' al-'Amm*)). Also treaties are to be upheld, even if it would overrule certain Shari'a rulings, if the treaties sustain peace and welfare for Muslim societies. The pro-abolishment side has therefore clear Shari'a grounds to stand on. The uniqueness of the Letter's pro-abolishment stance is that it is the first time such a large collective of Sunni scholars have used these arguments to reject slavery in such unequivocal terms, and even declaring it a *Fitna* and *Fasad fi-lArdh*. The anti-abolishment arguments by ISIS are not very convincing, and do not go beyond the mere establishment of its historical practice in the Sunna, and its connection to spoils of war in Jihad. For the majority of classical scholars, it would

13. It is forbidden in Islam to force people to convert.¹⁰⁶

be hard to argue that God *desires* slavery. It wasn't called an *Athar al-Kufr* for nothing. But ISIS uses this so-called revival of an abandoned Sunna as a symbol of anti-modernism and anti-Western humanist hegemony. ISIS is very selective in their 'revival of the Sunna', for example they logically do not revive the Sunna of riding camels or using swords instead of assault rifles, therefore these 'revivals' are used for their anti-modernism symbolism (as also with the Jizya replacing citizenship and general taxes, and Zakat replacing taxes). Also the sexism involved in its symbolism should not be discounted, which is seemingly a very powerful attraction for the adolescent soldiers ISIS attracts. Also the fear of the Letter writers that ISIS revival of slavery is a cause for Islamophobia, neglects to address that stirring up Islamophobia is part of ISIS strategy ('eliminating the gray zone'). ISIS is not interested in propagation (*dawa*) to non-Muslims, it is only interested in forcing Muslims to choose sides by attracting them through ISIS' actions, or by driving them out of non-Muslim lands by stirring up Islamophobia with those same actions. Landau-Tasserou, *Ibid*, 12. On al-Azhar's approach to slavery, see: Dar al-ifta al-Misriyya, "Fatawa - why didn't Islam abolish slavery immediately?", 2016, accessed juli 17, 2016, <http://eng.dar-alifta.org/foreign/ViewFatwa.aspx?ID=6830>. Dar al-ifta al-Misriyya, "Fatawa - slavery has no place in today's Islam", 2016, accessed juli 17, 2016, <http://eng.dar-alifta.org/foreign/ViewFatwa.aspx?ID=10759>. On (classical and modern) Islam and slavery, see: Akgündüz, *Islamic Public Law*, 75-81. Ahmed Akgündüz, *Ottoman Harem: The Male and Female Slavery in Islamic Law* (Istanbul: IUR Press, 2015), 91-140. Al-Zuhayli, *Al-Fiqh Al-Islamiyyu*, 3:36-49, 770, 774. Schacht, *Ibid*, 127-130. William G. Clarence-Smith, *Islam and the Abolition of Slavery* (United Kingdom: C Hurst & Co Publishers, 2005). E. C. Haven van der, "The Bey, the Mufti, and the Scattered Pearls: Shari'a and Political Leadership in Tunisia's Age of Reform 1800-1864", (n.p., 2006). Maulana Saeed Ahmad, *Slavery in Islam (al-Riqq fi al-Islam)* (Karachi: Darul Ishaat, 2000). Mashood A. Baderin, *International Human Rights and Islamic Law* (Oxford: Oxford University Press, USA, 2005), 86-88. Muhammad Rashid Rida, *The Muhammadan Revelation* (United States: Al-Saadawi Publications, U.S., 1996), 142 - 148. "Muslim slaves in early modern Europe: A forgotten history of slavery", Leiden Islamblog, june 16, 2016, accessed juli 17, 2016, <http://leiden-islamblog.nl/articles/muslim-slaves-in-early-modern-europe-a-forgotten-history-of-slavery>. Majid Khadduri, *War and Peace in the Law of Islam* (Baltimore: The John Hopkins Press, 1959), 128-32. On concubinage, see: Hina Azam, *Sexual Violation in Islamic Law: Substance, Evidence, and Procedure* (United Kingdom: Cambridge University Press, 2015), 84-88, 120-169. Khadduri, *Islamic Law of Nations*, 114-129. On modern objections to slavery in Islam, see: Maher Hathout, *In pursuit of justice: The jurisprudence of human rights in Islam* (United States: Muslim Public Affairs Council, 2006), 343-61. On consensus and Natural Law in Islamic law: Auda, *Ibid*, 108-111. Al-Raysuni, *Ibid*, 234-244. Al-Zuhayli, *Usul al-Fiqh al-Islamiyyu*, 1:465-570, 2:266-267. Abu Bakr al-Razi al-Jassas, *Usul al-Jassas almasammā al-Fusul fi al'Usul* (Beirut: Dār al-Kutub al'Ilmiyya, 2010), 2:100 - 101. Anver M Emon, *Islamic natural law theories* (New York: Oxford University Press, USA, 2010). On ISIS' argument for slavery, see their magazine 'Dabiq': Umm Sumayyah al-Muhajirah, "Slavegirls or Prostitutes?", *Dabiq* 9 (2015), 44-49, accessed juli 17, 2016, <http://media.clarionproject.org/files/islamic-state/isis-isil-islamic-state-magazine-issue%2B9-they-plot-and-allah-plots-sex-slavery.pdf>. On ISIS and *Siyasa al-Shari'a*, see: William Cants and Mara Revkin, "Experts weigh in (part 5): How does ISIS approach Islamic scripture?", may 13, 2015, accessed juli 17, 2016, <http://www.brookings.edu/blogs/markaz/posts/2015/05/12-isis-approach-to-scripture-revkin>. On ISIS' Islamophobia strategy: Murtaza Hussain, *Islamic state's goal: "Eliminating the Grayzone" of coexistence between Muslims and the west*, (The Intercept), november 17, 2015, <https://theintercept.com/2015/11/17/islamic-states-goal-eliminating-the-grayzone-of-coexistence-between-muslims-and-the-west/>.

¹⁰⁶ Letter, *Ibid*, 19. Here the Letter discusses coercion into ways: 1) To force non-Muslims to become Muslim. 2) To force Muslims to adhere to one interpretation of Islamic law. Here the Letter claims the famous "There is no compulsion in religion" verse (Q.2:256) was revealed after the conquest of Mecca (*fath Makka*), which is a minority claim. The majority of Qur'an commentators say the verse is revealed in the early Medinan phase, and I

haven't found any *tafsir* or '*Ulum al-Qur'an*' work mentioning otherwise, except the *tafsirs* of Abu Hassan al-Muqatil (d. 767), who states it is revealed after verse 5:105 (a late Medinan verse), and Abu Layth al-Samarqandi (d. 986) whereby the latter does not refer to the moment of revelation, but to when the verse is absolutely enforced: "Meaning there is no forcing anyone to the religion [of Islam] after the conquest of Mecca and the submission of the Arabs to Islam." (This commentary is also attributed to the Prophetic companion Ibn Abbas (d. 687)). Interestingly enough, this would prove with certainty that all verses on the obligation of Jihad are specific for the Meccan pagans and no one else (the latter being already the majority opinion). This way 2:256 would abrogate or specify 9:5 instead of the other way around as some exegetes have stated. But the Letter could still have simply used the majority opinion of it being early Medinan (and therefore revealed before 9:5), which also did not see 2:256 or the other 'lenient' verses abrogated by the 'belligerent' verses as Landau-Tasserion incorrectly claims. The only absolute abrogation (*mansukh 'amm*) claim on which is agreed upon is made by the Prophetic companion Ibn Masud (d. 653), whereby some scholars such as al-Nasafi say a majority agrees to this without specifying. The majority of scholars understood verse 2:256 in a threefold manner: 1) This verse proves faith in God is only to be established through reason and the heart, and never through force (by God or humans). 2) This verse proves the acceptability of the Jizya as a means for non-Muslims (the commentators generally state the verse is about *Ahl al-Kitab*, Zoroastrians and all other unbelievers) to attain citizenship with religious freedom within the Islamic lands (as discussed above at fn. 103, as the Jizya is only taken from healthy wealthy males it cannot be seen as a tax to retain their religion). This option, both of freedom and citizenship, was denied to the healthy Arab pagan males (i.e. Meccan Quraysh), which is a redundant exclusion after the first century. 3) There is no coercion and hardship in religion concerning the performance of religious duties, which is used against the Kharajites. Because of this threefold use, there is no need to see it as abrogated, as only the second point is specified (*khass*) by excluding Arab pagans because, as the pre-modern exegete Thani Allah al-Mazhari (d. 1810) states, they caused corruption on earth through their oppression and aggression. But as children, women, elderly, clergy, blind, and sick are excluded from both being killed, forced and paying the Jizya, it is clear, according to al-Mazhari, that the religious freedom of 2:256 also includes Arab pagans (the only question revolved around them being allowed to stay in the Arab peninsula, to leave them alone, or to enslave them). Therefore the idea that this verse (and the other verses mentioned by the Letter), according to pre-modern exegetes notions, cannot be used for modern concepts of religious freedom, is false. This verse (and many others) is also used by modern *Usuli* scholars as Ahmed al-Raysuni to reject the punishment for apostasy, because both the text itself, but especially the cause of revelation (*sabab al-Nuzul*), can lead to no other conclusion. According to the majority of commentators the verse was revealed because several sons of a Medinan *Ansar* (the first Medinan converts to Islam who supported the Meccans after their migration) decided to travel along with a Christian merchant to become Christians. Their father went to the Prophet and asked what to do, and before he could reply, this verse was revealed. This context is generally taken to mean that as the sons were considered Muslims, that their apostasy to Christianity was allowed by God by specifically revealing verse 2:256. On of the Letter signatories, Shaykh Bin Bayyah, also has stated on several conferences that he views the punishment for apostasy as 'outdated': "That was to protect the religion ... but it is no longer the mentality for the age we live in, so when you look at the universal principle of Islam it is to attract people towards religion." However, he said, in the current age applying apostasy law will cause more people to leave religion than to join it so it has an opposite effect." Haneen Dajani, *Outdated religious laws must be changed, UAE forum hears*, (TheNational), april 29, 2015, <http://www.thenational.ae/uae/outdated-religious-laws-must-be-changed-uae-forum-hears>. (on apostasy, see above at fn. 102). ISIS uses a very narrow and incoherent Shafi'i reading of such verses to only accept the Jizya from *Ahl al-Kitab*, and to see the whole world come under the ruling of their idea of the caliphate. Classical scholars rejected the idea that the whole world would be ruled by the Shari'a, both out of pragmatism (it seemed an impossible notion), and because of Qur'anic texts stating otherwise (and Hadith which discuss the end of times). The third use of this verse directly relates to the way ISIS enforces its interpretation of Islam on other Muslims. Their religious police (*hisba*) is a direct copy of the religious police in Saudi-Arabia and Iran, and is a modern state-apparatus version of 'forbidding wrong and commanding good'. In pre-modern Islam the idea of a police force slowly emerged from market censors and the military guard, but

14. It is forbidden in Islam to deny women their rights.¹⁰⁷

mainly was focused on public crime and mediation. Throughout Muslim history, fanatical mobs of especially the Athariyya school of thought, has had moments of policing a city or attacking who they considered heretics, And these were either quenched by the Muslim ruler, or allowed to play out their rage to prevent worsen outbreaks. But as far as I know has there never been an official apparatus that can be compared to today's religious police by Saudi-Arabia, Iran and ISIS, which in a sense is the bureaucratization of the fanatical Athariyya mobs. The enforcement of their interpretation of Islam, especially concerning women's dress and free movement, which represents a minority opinion (the *niqab* is rejected by the majority of classical scholars as an obligation), rejects the classical allowed disagreement (*ikhtilaf*) in Sunni Islam and the personal responsibility one has in front of God concerning private sins.. In classical Islam, the only time the laws of Islam are enforced by the state, is when there is a violation of a divine or human right, which are encapsulated by the penal laws (*hudud*). So there is minimal *religious* enforcement by the classical state. Al-Mazhari, and other exegetes, points out that verse 2:256 is applicable to the Kharijites who demanded other Muslims to act upon their Islam or be killed as apostates. It is also here where surprisingly enough Landau-Tasseron incorrectly claims that Yusuf al-Qaradawi is one of the authors of the Letter. He is not even one of its signatories. Landau-Tasseron is probably unaware of the animosity between al-Qaradawi and al-Azhar since the coup against Moursi, and probably assumes that with these, according to her seemingly, Islamist initiatives, al-Qaradawi must be involved (as she constantly mentions him throughout her review as an example of the, according to her, deceiving liberalism expounded by 'moderate' Islam). Landau-Tasseron, *Ibid*, 12. On Qur'an 2:256 and religious freedom, see: Abu Hassan al-Muqatil, *Tafsir al-Muqatil* (Beirut: Dar al-Kutub al-'Ilmiyya, 2003), 1:136 – 137. Al-Samarqandi, *Ibid*, 1:224. Majd al-Din al-Fayruzabadi, *Tanwir al-Miqbas min Tafsir Ibn Abbas* (Beirut: Dar al-Kutub al-'Ilmiyya, 2008), 47. Al-Baydawi, *Ibid*, 1:140. Al-Mazhari, *Ibid*, 1:351-352. Al-Nasafi, *Ibid*, 1:152. Al-Maturidi, *Ibid*, 2:238-240. Al-Burusawi, *Ibid*, 1:412. Al-Alusi, *Ibid*, 3:19-20. Emon, *Ibid*, 65-69, 75-76, 102-105. Tahir-ul-Qadri, *Ibid*, 157-160. Patricia Crone, "No compulsion in religion: Q. 2: 256 in Mediaeval and modern interpretation", in *The Qur'anic Pagans and Related Matters* (Leiden: Brill Academic Publishers, 2016). Ahmed Al-Raysouni, "Freedom of religion and Apostasy in Islam", june 25, 2009, <http://www.virtualmosque.com/islam-studies/hot-topics/freedom-of-religion-and-apostasy-in-islam-by-dr-ahmed-raysuni/>. Mohammad Hashim Kamali, *Shari'ah law: An introduction* (Oxford, England: Oneworld Publications, 2008), 173–174, 220–221. On classical notions of policing, see: Michael A. Cook, *Commanding Right and Forbidding Wrong in Islamic Thought* (United Kingdom: Cambridge University Press, 2001). Akgündüz, *Ibid*, 288-295. Abu-l Hassan al-Mawardi, *The ordinances of government: Al-Ahkam As-Sultaniyyah w'at wilayat al Dinniyya* (Reading, UK: Garnet Publishing, 2000), 337–62. Yusuf Qaradawi, *State in Islam* (Cairo: El-Falah, 1998), 170–88. On Qaradawi and al-Azhar: "Brotherhood-linked cleric Qaradawi quits Cairo's al-Azhar", *Alarabiya*, december 3, 2013, <http://english.alarabiya.net/en/News/middle-east/2013/12/03/Brotherhood-linked-cleric-Qaradawi-quits-Cairo-s-al-Azhar-.html>.

¹⁰⁷ Letter, *Ibid*, 19-20. Here the Letter condemns ISIS' extreme anti-gender mixing position, which is simply an extension of Saudi-Arabia's anti-mixing laws. The opinions on gender-mixing (*ikhtilat*) in public spaces, and which dress codes are obligatory or preferred, differs among the schools over the centuries and geographical locations. This is an area of Islamic law which depends heavily on custom ('*urf*') and less on sourcetexts. The Letter also clearly sees the ISIS proscribed *niqab* (faceveil) and *khimar* (loose gown covering the whole body) as based on 'their whims' compared to the sourcetext proscribed headscarf. Although women in ISIS are allowed, and in some cases are obliged, to attend certain classes on creed and ISIS' law-texts, ISIS held territories have shot down elementary and high school classes for women. Which was also done in Afghanistan under Taliban rule. In classical Islam, there have always been female teachers and students (especially female Hadith scholars), who taught in public and private (even Ibn Taymiyya studied under several women and praised them as the best scholars he ever studied with). Male and female access to elementary studies in classical madrassas depended on the liberality of their families to invest in schools and teachers, whereby elementary teachings were normal for

15. It is forbidden in Islam to deny children their rights.¹⁰⁸

both genders in urban areas, but higher studies were generally reserved for men as women were expected to become housewives. Only with the advent of the 19th century do we see, whereby Eastern developments followed Europe closely, a systemization of education which made girl education obligatory and slowly gave women access to higher studies. ISIS goes beyond mere gender conservatism, and is known to keep single and widowed women in special houses where they are kept until they are married. The amount and form of coercion or pressure involved to marry ISIS fighters is unknown (apart from the poor conditions in these women-houses). Classical Islam forbade forced marriages, but ISIS makes disobedience and protest against their commands as signs of apostasy, and probably also uses this to coerce women to be arranged to certain fighters. Many of the women migrated to the Islamic State (many who are below the age of 20) want to fight, but accept the role of housewife and produce children. Local Sunni families are harassed to marry their women to ISIS fighters. On Islamic law and women, see: Khaled Abou El Fadl, *Speaking in god's name: Islamic law, authority, and women* (Oxford: Oneworld Publications, 2001). Susan Spector, *Women in classical Islamic law: A survey of the sources* (Netherlands: Brill Academic Publishers, 2009). Leila Ahmed, *Women and gender in Islam: Historical roots of a modern debate*, 2de ed. (New Haven: Yale University Press, 1992). On women and classical scholarship, see: Mohammad Akram Nadwi, *Al-Muhaddithat: The women scholars in Islam* (United Kingdom: Interface Publications, 2007). Asma Sayeed, *Women and the transmission of religious knowledge in Islam* (United Kingdom: Cambridge University Press, 2013). On the treatment of women by ISIS: Elise Keppler, *Iraq: Women suffer under ISIS*, (n.p.: Human Rights Watch, 2016), <https://www.hrw.org/news/2016/04/05/iraq-women-suffer-under-isis>. Institute for Strategic Dialogue, *Becoming Mulan? Female Western Migrants to ISIS*, (n.p., 2015), http://www.strategicdialogue.org/wp-content/uploads/2016/02/ISDJ2969_Becoming_Mulan_01.15_WEB.pdf. Mah-Rukh Ali, *ISIS and Propaganda: How ISIS Exploits Women*, (n.p.: Reuters Institute for the Study of Journalism, 2015), <https://reutersinstitute.politics.ox.ac.uk/sites/default/files/Isis%20and%20Propaganda-%20How%20Isis%20Exploits%20Women.pdf>. On women treatment in Saudi-Arabia: Human Rights Watch, *Boxed in: Women and Saudi Arabia's Male Guardianship System*, (n.p.: Human Rights Watch, 2016), <https://www.hrw.org/report/2016/07/16/boxed/women-and-saudi-arabias-male-guardianship-system>.

¹⁰⁸ Letter, *Ibid*, 20. Here the Letter tries tackle with a grey area in Islamic law: notions of maturity in classical thought related to bodily maturity (*bulugh*) and ethical responsibility (*taklif*). When it comes to *bulugh*, the majority of Fiqh scholars generally recommended an age of 15 or 18 years, whereby some mention that founding imams as imam Malik and Abū Hanifa mentioned ages 21 and 25. There was therefore a wide scope of age, similar to modern discussions, on bodily maturity and how this relates to individual self-reliance and responsibility. These discussions on maturity were generally based on personal reasoning, but there was one Hadith wherein the Prophet Muhammad rejected a boy to fight when he was 14, but accepted him to join battles when he had turned 15. Especially the Shafi'i use this Hadith to determine the minimal age for penal punishments to be 15. Early Hanafi and Maliki disagreed on this Hadith and its implications (if through analogy (*qiyas*) it can be extended to marriageable age and punishable before the law), but in general, from the ages 15 to 18, a boy was seen as ethically responsible for performed crimes and therefore punishable with the *Hudud*. Mullājīyūn al-Ḥanafī, *Ibid*, 211-212. Al-Māturīdī, *Ibid*, 4:316. Ibn al-'Arabī, *Ibid*, 1:418. ISIS on the other hand uses boys much younger than 15 in their videos of training camps and public executions, and several reports also stated boys under 15 were killed for ritual and creedal violations. When it comes to exposure to public executions, in the medieval world this was normal as these were public displays of just order and political power, but it was not allowed to be executed by untrained hands. The way ISIS uses and indoctrinates children is appalling and hard to defend from a classical Sunni perspective. See; Christian Lange, *Justice, punishment and the medieval Muslim imagination* (United Kingdom: Cambridge University Press, 2008), 173–74, 246. On ISIS' treatment of children, see: "UN Group: ISIS committing horrific crimes against children", *News* (TheBlot

16. It is forbidden in Islam to enact legal punishments (*hudud*) without following the correct procedures that ensure justice and mercy.¹⁰⁹

Magazine), februari 10, 2015, <https://www.theblot.com/un-group-isis-committing-horrific-crimes-against-children-7734579>.

¹⁰⁹ Letter, *Ibid*, 20. Here the Letter emphasizes that the penal punishments (*hudud*) are undeniably part of the Shari'a. This is not a direct endorsement of their application, but first of all an acknowledgement of them being part of revelatory sourcetexts. In classical and modern Sunnism there are generally four possible approaches to the application of the *Hudud*: 1) Make the requirements for the application of the *Hudud* as strict as possible whereby their application is almost impossible to apply in court. This approach is the majority position in Sunnism and is also endorsed here by the Letter. 2.a) Make the *Hudud* contextual by seeing their causal rationale or occasioning factor (*'illa*) be specific to a certain historical or sociological context (as is done by several modern scholars with the punishment of apostasy, and with all *Hudud* by modernists as Abdullah Saeed and Nasr Abu Zayd). 2.b) Or seeing these rationales as so specific that their circumstances (*mahal*) rarely take place (generally mixed with approach 1 and 2.c. This is a classical position among many *Usuliyun* such as Abu Zayd al-Dabusi (d. 1039) and Fakhr al-Din al-Razi (d. 1209). Al-Azhar uses this as a reason why the *Hudud* cannot be applied in modern times). 2.c) Or focusing on these rationales as first of all demanding a deterrence for these crimes whereby the provided revealed punishment is only a maximum indicator of a possible spectrum of punishments (i.e. the punishments are only the means, the rationales the ends. This is classically combined with approach 1 and have become the norm among the later Hanafi school who judged discretionary punishments (*ta'zir*) to be just as an effective deterrence as the *Hudud*. This Hanafi approach also prepared the way for the Tanzimat reforms in which the classical *Hudud* and *Ta'zir* were replaced with French penal law. This replacing is not seen as abrogation, as their revelatory and active status are not denied. To understand the *Hudud* as providing a spectrum instead of a fixed punishment is also suggested by modernists as Muhammad Shahrur). 3.a) The *Hudud* are abrogated or made non-applicable by order of Muslim leadership (such as the lifting of the *Hudud* by the second caliph 'Umar al-Khattab (d. 644) during famines, and the rejection of stoning by the Ottoman sultan Mehmet IV in 1680). 3.b) Or abrogation through consensus (as is partially done today with the punishment of apostasy), 3.c) or abrogation by reason (The classical Hanafi theologian Abu Mansur al-Maturidi (d. 944) allowed *naskh bil-ijtihad* in his commentary on verse 9:60, basing himself on Umar's lifting of the *Hudud*). 4) Reinterpret the harsh bodily punishments into less harsh or symbolic punishments as is done by modernists as Edip Yuksel. The Letter combines approaches 1, 2.b and 3.a, whereby there are specific requirements in the application of the *Hudud*, and that the *Hudud* cannot be applied in times of war (which they compare to Umar's lifting of the *Hudud* during famine). Classically, the *Hudud* were never central to Islamic law (the majority of Fiqh texts do not discuss them), as they were seen as a form of public law which did not concern the daily lives of Muslims (while rituals, family law, and trade law were), and their application was seen as a rarity. The Prophet Muhammad emphasized that the *Hudud* must be avoided and ordered judges to refrain from applying in the case of the smallest doubt of guilt. This avoidance element was the basis for extensive rules on accepted witnesses and testimonies, whereby any missing condition of the demanded procedural elements (as four witnesses with adultery) made it impossible for a judge to apply it. Also a judge was not obliged to apply the *Hudud* even when all conditions were fulfilled if he felt that an alternative punishment achieved a similar deterrent and punishing effect. Therefore this classical reluctance for the *Hudud* cannot be explained to its development 'under Muslim regimes' as Landau-Tasseron states, as this reluctance is directly based on Prophetic sayings and practice. It is rather the opposite whereby Islamic law was used by Muslim scholars as a buffer against regime brutality. ISIS' application of the *Hudud* is an extension of Saudi-Arabia's application, but with added spectacle such as the throwing of suspected homosexual males of buildings. They base this application on an opinion related by Ibn Abbas, but has always been rejected by the Sunni schools. The Hanafi school for the majority rejected capital punishment for homosexual acts, the other schools compared it to

17. It is forbidden in Islam to torture people.¹¹⁰

adultery and therefore applied the *Hudud* rulings of adultery to it. The centrality of the *Hudud* within Islamist thought as the main expression of Shari'a rule is a modernist construction (see also fn. 114 below). Due to this centrality, they avoid or overlook the classical reluctance to apply them. The rate of 20th-21st century *Hudud* applications by Iran and Saudi-Arabia is unprecedented in Islamic history. ISIS' executions are part of their management of savagery and therefore ignore classical humanistic protocols (see also fn. 110-111 below). Landau-Tasserou, *Ibid*, 14. Koçak, *Ibid*, 234-236. Al-Khassaf, *Ibid*, 135-136. Akgündüz, *Islamic Public Law*, 303-432, 525-592. Rabb, *Ibid*, 48-228. Al-Zuhayli, *Al-Fiqh Al-Islamiyyu*, 5:711-815, 6:19-562. Abu Zayd al-Dabusi, *Taqwim Al-Adila Fi Usul Al-Fiqh* (Beirut: Al-Maktaba al-'Assriya, 2006), 370 – 372, 397 – 398. Al-Jassas, *Mukhtasar Ikhtilaf al-Ulama*, 3:277-463. Khaled Abou El Fadl, *Reasoning with god: Reclaiming Shari'ah in the modern age* (United States: Rowman & Littlefield Publishers, 2014), 292–303. Schacht, *Ibid*, 90–93, 175–198. Elyse Semerdjian, “*Off the straight path*”: *Illicit sex, law, and community in Ottoman Aleppo* (United States: Syracuse University Press, 2002), 29–60. Muḥammad Shahrur and Dale F. Eickelman, *The Qur'an, Morality and Critical Reason: The Essential Muhammad Shahrur*, ed. Andreas Christmann (Boston: Brill Academic Publishers, 2009), 177 – 218. Al-Maturidi, *Ibid*, 5:406-407. Dar al-ifta al-Misriyya, “Ḥudūd in the Islamic Sharia”, accessed juli 8, 2016, <http://eng.dar-alifta.org/foreign/ViewArticle.aspx?ID=358>. “Applying Shari'ah in today's world”, accessed juli 8, 2016, <http://eng.dar-alifta.org/foreign/ViewArticle.aspx?ID=109>. Abdullah Saeed, *Interpreting the Quran: Towards a contemporary approach* (United Kingdom: Taylor & Francis, 2005), 116–125. Edip Yuksel, Layth Saleh Al-Shaiban, and Martha Schulte-Nafeh, *Quran: A Reformist Translation* (United States: Brainbow Press, 2010), 21, 119-120, 240.

¹¹⁰ Letter, *Ibid*, 20-21. As Landau-Tasserou correctly states, it is almost impossible to find any source of Islamic law which allows torturing people for whatever reason. That torture was applied by Muslim rulers in the past can be stated without doubt, but such acts lay outside, and also goes against, Islamic law discourse on treatment of prisoners. Islamic law forbade torture to obtain information, confessions, or as punishments themselves, as harm to bodies could only be done on the battlefield, or by proscribed punishments (*hudud* and *ta'zir*). The general rule is that the method of execution itself is never meant as the punishment, and can only be a means. Therefore executions must be applied as fast and least painful as possible, which is why beheadings by the swords by experienced swordsmen were preferred in classical times. Exceptional punishments as stoning for adultery were therefore provided by extensive details on which stones to be used to prevent a prolonged execution, and crucifixion (as given in Qur'an 5:33 for highway robbery and rebellion) was done after the execution. ISIS uses their executions as spectacles both the attract new recruits and to intimidate enemy soldiers and local population. And is part of their strategy of savagery. As stated in fn. 101, Muslim captives were not allowed to be killed due to being soldiers for a rival Muslim governance, nor do the *Hudud* apply to them. Landau-Tasserou is seemingly unaware of these general rules when she discusses ISIS' justification for burning the Jordanian pilot in 2015. In this case, ISIS referred to a Shafi'i opinion, based on Qur'an 16:126, which theoretically discussed in what ways retaliations could be possible. But a tradition stating the Prophet forbade executions by fire was generally accepted, and therefore made retaliation by fire forbidden. As this is such a known tradition, it directly exposes the incoherence of ISIS. There are also multiple Qur'anic verses and Hadith which clearly condemn maltreatment and torture, such as the Hadith: “Allah, Most High, will punish those who torture people in this world.” Al-Zuhayli, *Al-Fiqh Al-Islamiyyu*, 5:813, 6:86-87. Landau-Tasserou, *Ibid*, 14-15. Shokry M. El-Dakkak, *State's Crimes against Humanity: Genocide, Deportation, and Torture from the Perspectives of International and Islamic Laws* (Kuala Lumpur: A.S. Noordeen, 2000), 152 – 179. Emad Mostaque, *Islamic state and the “management of savagery”*, (Reuters), november 17, 2015, <http://blogs.reuters.com/great-debate/2015/11/16/islamic-state-and-the-management-of-savagery/>. Shiraz Maher, *Shiraz Maher on Isis: The management of savagery*, juli 12, 2016, <http://www.newstatesman.com/culture/2016/07/shiraz-maher-isis-management-savagery>.

18. It is forbidden in Islam to disfigure the dead.¹¹¹

19. It is forbidden in Islam to attribute evil acts to God.¹¹²

20. It is forbidden in Islam to destroy the graves and shrines of Prophets and Companions.¹¹³

¹¹¹ Letter, *Ibid*, 21. Mutilation (*mathla*) of corpses is forbidden as stated by vast the majority of scholars. As stated by al-Baydawi on Qur'an 2:190: "And do not transgress by begin the fighting, or by fighting those aligned through pacts ('*ahd*), or through surprise attacks without any warning, or mutilation, or fighting those that are forbidden to fight. God doesn't love those that transgress and He doesn't want any goodness for them." Al-Baydawi, *Ibid*, 1:127-128. Some allowed for the ruler to display corpses of rebels, political enemies, or people despised by the population if it served public policy and order. Crucifixion of the body after execution for highway robbery and rebellion, was also a means to display the body. ISIS has used crucifixion against enemy soldiers, spies, and Christians, which clearly fall outside the original ruling allowing crucifixion. The hanging of heads on spikes and on fences (or playing soccer with the heads) violates the funerary rites of these victims. But just as with their excessive executions, mutilations are part of ISIS' management of savagery. Again the Letter complains about the Islamophobic effect of these acts, while these are part of their strategy. Lange, *Ibid*, 63, 72, 185.

¹¹² Letter, *Ibid*, 21. Here the Letter attacks ISIS' collapsing of their acts with that of God, which is a typical aspect of ISIS' Salafi-Wahhabism creedal fatalism. Classical Sunnism, represented by rational-theological schools of Ash'arism and Maturidism, sees God as the creator of all acts performed by and within creation, but the created acts are based on the results of human free will. God's eternal pre-knowledge knows these results of human free will and accordingly creates the acts connected to them. In this way, classical Sunnism (especially the Maturidi school) tries to distinguish between human will, God's will and decree controlling creation, and what God desires or prefers of the acts within creation. Therefore classical Sunnism stated God's writing of fate on the Well-Preserved Tablet (*Lawh al-Mahfuz*) is by description (of the human freely willed acts) and not by commanding (these acts). In this way humans are responsible for their acts, while God remains the sole creator. God also wills evil to exist, but doesn't desire it. As stated by the Maturidi theologian Mulla Ali al-Qari (d. 1606): "Good is attributed to Allah, as He is responsible in every sense for its favorable bestowal. As for [what seems to be] evil, He created it for some wise purpose, and based on that wise purpose, it is counted from among His favors; Allah Most High does not do evil. Everything He does is good and for the best, as the Messenger said, addressing Allah, 'The good is all in Your hands and the evil cannot be imputed to You', which means, 'You do not create anything purely and wholly evil, because everything You create consist of some wisdom by which it is considered good, even though it is sometimes considered evil for some people; this makes it a partial and relative evil. As far as it being pure or completely evil, Allah is transcendent of that. This is why evil cannot be solely attributed to Allah; instead it can be counted as being from among the generality of His creation, as in, 'Allah is the creator of all things' (Qur'an 13:16)." Mulla Ali al-Qari, *Sharh al-Fiqh al-Akbar* (Beirut: Dar al-Kutub al-'Ilmiyya, 2007), 80. Ahmad Ibn Muhammad Maghnisawi, *Imam Abu Hanifa's Al-Fiqh Al-Akbar explained* (United Kingdom: White Thread Press, 2007), 108–13. Salafi-Wahhabism states that man has free will, but at the same time that human will is subject to God's will. "Meaning of belief in al-qadar (the divine will and decree)", april 19, 2010, accessed juli 24, 2016, <https://islamqa.info/en/34732>. The problem of course with the Letter's argument, is that ISIS doesn't view their acts as evil, or at least as an evil forbidden by God's law. In their view, their killings and savagery are allowed means to serve a just end: the triumphant rule of the caliphate through which God's word is triumphant. Classical Islam always viewed political rule as a means to uphold justice, and was never seen as an end in itself.

21. Armed insurrection is forbidden in Islam for any reason other than clear disbelief by the ruler and not allowing people to pray.¹¹⁴

¹¹³ Letter, *Ibid*, 21-22. Here the Letter argues against ISIS' destruction of tombs and mosques with graves in them. Although it is clearly avoided by the Letter, but this discussion centers around the concept of relics and sainthood used as intercessional means (*tawassul*), which is the main point of contention between classical Sunnism and Salafi-Wahhabism. The latter views it as *Shirk*, and therefore sees the destruction of anything that could remotely be made part of Muslim worship as a form of worship itself. The Letter here argues that visiting graves reminds people of the Hereafter, which is a general statement mentioned by many classical scholars, but this avoids the discussion on why certain graves are made into tombs or be encompassed by a mosque. Generally, classical Sunnism refers to, as does the Letter here, to the simple historical fact that the Prophet's grave was always part of the original mosque. Salafi-Wahhabism uses several Hadith to counter the idea that the Prophet allowed a tomb for himself: "Allah cursed the Jews and the Christians for taking the graves of their prophets as mosques" en "O, Allah do not make my grave an object of worship; Allah cursed those who took the graves of their prophets as mosques." Classical Sunni scholars as al-Baydawi explained this Hadith as referring to taking tombs as prayer-directions (*qibla*), and not as a total dismissal of tombs. A book of traditions related to Abu Hanifa (d. 767) mentioned also : "Someone informed me that they had seen the grave of Prophet, the grave of Abu Bakr, and the grave of Umar with 'mounds on top of them protruding prominently from the ground' and on them pieces of white clay." Proving that these graves were above ground and plastered in the first century of Islam. On tombs and *Tawassul*, see: "Tawassul (supplicating Allah through an intermediary)", juli 28, 2012, accessed juli 24, 2016, <http://islamqa.org/hanafi/daruliftaa/8548>. "Tawassul(Waseela)", accessed juli 24, 2016, http://www.ahlus-sunna.com/index.php?option=com_content&view=article&id=57&Itemid=116. "Tribulations of the Wahabies", accessed juli 24, 2016, http://www.sunna.info/antiwahabies/wahhabies/htm/fitnat_al_wahhabiyyah.htm.

¹¹⁴ Letter, *Ibid*, 22-23. For ISIS, the non-application of the *Hudud* is a cause for *takfir* on the political ruler and his administration (see fn. 90 above. This accusation was also issued by the early Wahhabi against the Ottomans). Classical Sunnism on the other hand saw it as being part of the major sins, but not a cause to rebel against the ruler. The general Qur'an verse cited by Islamists on the obligatory nature of applying every single aspect (of the Islamist's notion) of the Shari'a is: "And whoever does not judge by what God has revealed, then it is those who are disbelievers (*al-Kafirun*). (Qur'an 5:44)" This statement is repeated with different endings in verses 5:45 (wrongdoers, *al-Zalimun*) and 5:47 (sinners, *al-Fasiqun*). According to the Prophetic companion Ibn Abbas, and the majority of commentators, these verses were not revealed about the Shari'a, but is specific (*khass*) for the Jews. The verses clearly discuss Jewish law in the Torah (as is stated in 5:44) which the Jews in Medina were reluctant to apply in the case of a Jewish adulterer. They approached Muhammad as judge and mediator, whereby he asked the Jewish ruling for adultery, for which they replied stoning. They hoped Muhammad would rather apply the Qur'anic ruling of flogging (Qur'an 24:2). It is this context to which verses 5:44-48 reply too. Another occasion of revelation refers to a case of retaliation whereby a person of the Jewish tribe Bani Nadir killed somebody from the Jewish tribe Bani Qurayza, which they tried to settle through bloodmoney (*diyya*). At that point verses 5:44-45 were revealed which contained the 'eye for an eye' ruling from the Torah with the added option of forgiveness. Also another dominant interpretation of these verses is that 5:44's unbelief refers to the Jews, 5:45's wrongdoing to the Christians, and 5:47's transgression to Muslims. But the most important interpretation, which is also referred to here by the Letter, is related also from Ibn Abbas in which he counters the Kharijite interpretation of these verses who used them to declare the fourth caliph Ali ibn Abi Talib (d. 661) a disbeliever when he allowed a settlement between him and Mu'awiyya (d. 680) to end the first Muslim civil war (656-661). Because of this settlement, which the proto-Kharijites saw as violating the Qur'anic precepts, declared him an unbeliever and assassinated him. Ibn Abbas said that verses 5:44, 45, and 47 gave three levels of rejection or non-application of the Shari'a: Rejection of the Shari'a is unbelief (*Kufr*, 5:44),

ruling through disputed or heretical interpretations is wrongdoing (*Zulm*, 5:45), and leaving the Shari'a is transgression (*Fisq*, 5:47). And when he was asked about in what way rejecting the Shari'a is unbelief, he replied: "This is an unbelief which is without [real] unbelief (*kufr duna kufr*).” Meaning, it is an act of unbelief which belongs to the major sins, but does not negate one's faith-adherence. In this way, classical Sunnism rejected the notion that non-application of the Shari'a makes a ruler an unbeliever which would have made rebellion against him justified. As Landau-Tasserone points out, this politically quietist attitude is rejected by extremists as being part of the Murji'a theology they reject vehemently. But Landau-Tasserone strangely enough believes that the Kharijite reading of verse 5:44 is correct, even though the verse clearly mentions the Torah, is seemingly unaware of the multiple readings as provided here, and also misunderstands the Shari'a logic behind Sunni political quietism. Although this quietist attitude was logically encouraged by the political rulers, from a Shari'a perspective political quietism preserved the main objective of the Shari'a: to preserve life and reduce harm. Rebellion of the local population against its ruler and his professional army would, in the eyes of classical scholars, cause more bloodshed and destruction of life and property, than any tyranny could provide. If one wants to avoid tyranny, one should emigrate to other lands just as the Prophets have done before. Also there was a theological belief that God would remove unjust rulers (through, for example, disease) based on the interpretation of verse 11:117 which is understood to mean that God will not destroy any people for wrongdoing against God such as *Shirk* (violation of the *Huquq Allah*, divine rights), but they will be destroyed for any wrongdoing to other humans (violation of the *Huquq al-Nass*, human rights). Which provided the maxim: Rulership will remain with unbelief (*kufr*), but not with injustice (*zulm*). Classical Shari'a governance has from the very beginning of Islam applied a mix of Shari'a, local-customary law, and rulings provided by the ruler and his administration. Therefore this Kharijite accusation of unbelief technically applied to every Muslim ruler that ever lived. After the Kharijites dissipated in the third century (and became a new school, the Ibadi), it wasn't applied for fourteen centuries until Ibn Wahhab and his followers reintroduced this accusation against the Ottomans. But ISIS also does *takfir* on all Shi'ites, and on countries ruled through democracy, which both apply to Syria and Iraq, and the latter to almost all Muslim-majority countries. So from the *takfiri*-theology of ISIS, their rebellion is justified. The problem from a Sunni perspective with ISIS's theology is its rejection of dozens of Hadith that forbid the rebellion against a ruler who allows Muslims to observe their prayers, and the rejection of armed rebellion based on general consensus (even Ibn Taymiyya rejected armed rebellion. A minority of scholars allowed rebellion against an oppressive ruler, but only with approval of the majority of scholars and only if military resistance can be successfully organized as with the Abbasid revolution against the Umayyads, through which civilian bloodshed is averted). Just as, for example, with the rulings on prisoners of war, is the weight of the classical Islamic tradition against the *takfiri*-theology as upheld by ISIS and other extremists. And it is also this call for rebellion against any modern government and society which makes the comparison between modern extremists as ISIS and the classical Kharijites justified. And there is a general consensus in classical Islam that rebels should be fought (the majority of classical Fiqh texts discuss rebellion, brigandry, and apostasy under the same heading). This ruling is also used by Shaykh al-Yaqoubi to justify the Arab-Western coalition (i.e. Muslim and non-Muslim coalition) fighting ISIS as Islamically acceptable. And as the Letter states, this rejection of armed rebellion doesn't mean there are no other ways to depose an unjust ruler. Sadly it only provides the classical-theoretical example of a scholar-council who can depose and contract rulers (*ahl al-hall wa al-'aqd*). Technically such a council rarely ever existed, but it is also unclear who this council is today. With the rise of the Arab Spring there were multiple scholars in each country that were for or against the demonstrations and rebellions. Some of these scholars also saw the demonstrations as equal to rebellion, whereby any public criticism would be impossible. Others allowed demonstrations based on the Hadith that people can correct rulers through words. The classical rulings against rebellion have a humanitarian logic, and the countries who endure armed rebellions such as Syria and Libya, are clear examples how such rebellions are causes of major bloodshed and humanitarian disasters. At the same time are the classical rulings vague on public means to criticize, demonstrate against and depose the ruler, whereby the call by extremists to fight unjust rulers have gained much sympathy. Therefore a rethinking of Shari'a-allowed public criticism and deposing in modern democracies is required. Landau-Tasserone, *Ibid*, 16. On verses 5:44-45, 47, see: Shaykh Salim Al-Hilali, *A study*

22. It is forbidden in Islam to declare a caliphate without consensus from all Muslims.¹¹⁵

of the *Tafsir of Abdullah Ibn Abbas: Kufr Duna Kufr* (United Kingdom: Jamiah Media, 2013), 34-55. Al-Fayruzabadi, *Ibid*, 124. Al-Maturidi, *Ibid*, 3:527-528. Al-Baydawi, *Ibid*, 1:271, 475. Al-Mazhari, *Ibid*, 2:358-359, 3:498-499. Al-Alusi, *Ibid*, 6:443-444. On Shari'a and secular law in classical Islam, see: Linda T. Darling, *A history of social justice and political power in the middle east: The circle of justice from Mesopotamia to globalization* (New York: Taylor & Francis, 2012), 49–210. Akgündüz, *Ibid*, 418-432. On rebellion and protest against rulers, see: Khaled Abou El Fadl, *Rebellion and violence in Islamic law* (United Kingdom: Cambridge University Press, 2006), 32–294. Al-Zuhayli, *Al-Fiqh Al-Islamiyyu*, 6:77-95. Tahir-ul-Qadri, *Ibid*, 171-238. Al-Yaqoubi, *Ibid*, 28-30. Al-'izz, *Ibid*, 336-338. Al-Juwayni, *Ibid*, 234-235. Al-Mazidi, Ed., *Shuruh wa Hawashi al-'Aqa'id al-Nasafiyya*, 5:204-206. Muhammad S. El-Awa, *On the Political System of the Islamic State (Fi-l-Nizam al-Siyasi li-l-Duwalat al-Islamiyyah)* (Indiana: American Trust Publications, 1980), 113–16. Waardenburg, *Ibid*, 377-383. Lambton, *Ibid*, 38, 57, 61-64, 146, 284. Antony Black, *The History of Islamic Political Thought: From the Prophet to the Present* (Edinburgh: Edinburgh University Press, 2001), 27, 29, 75, 110. Shabbir Akhtar, *Islam as Political Religion: The Future of an Imperial Faith* (United Kingdom: Taylor & Francis, 2010), 176 – 177. *The Princeton encyclopedia of Islamic political thought* (United States: Princeton University Press, 2012), s.v. “Rebellion” by Sohail H. Hashmi, edited by Gerhard Bowering, Patricia Crone, and Wadad Kadi, 459–60. *The Princeton encyclopedia of Islamic political thought*, s.v. “Revolutions” by Melissa Finn, 470–71. For Muslim scholars' responses to the Arab Spring, see: *Profiles of Syrian Sunni clerics in the uprising*, (n.p.: Carnegie Endowment for International Peace, 2016), <http://carnegieendowment.org/syriaincrisis/51284>. Mark R Beissinger a.o., *Who participated in the Arab spring? A comparison of Egyptian and Tunisian revolutions*, (n.p., 2013), <http://www.princeton.edu/~mbeissin/beissinger.tunisiaegyptcoalitions.pdf>.

¹¹⁵ Letter, *Ibid*, 23. Here the Letter responds to the most unique claim made by ISIS: the re-instatement of the caliphate. The Letter states that: 1) The caliphate is an obligation upon the Muslim global community, 2) but it cannot be claimed by a small group over a small area without the consensus of the *Umma*. 3) Announcing the caliphate without consensus creates sedition (*fitna*) because it excludes the majority of Muslims, and 4) rival caliphates could emerge. 5) ISIS' leader al-Baghdadi stated in his first announcement that he was placed in authority of all the Muslims, while this authority claim only comes from a small group of several thousand (i.e. ISIS) which can never represent 1.6 billion Muslims. 6) This claim can therefore only lead to circular excommunication (*takfir*) whereby the majority of Muslims rejecting this caliphate is excommunicated by ISIS because they reject ISIS' claim. This was already shown by ISIS killing the head Sunni scholars of Mosul as they refused to acknowledge al-Baghdadi. If ISIS doesn't want to excommunicate the majority of Muslims, then they must accept that this same majority rejects their caliphate claim. 7) Real consensus is achieved by Muslim countries, organizations and scholars agreeing on a caliphate. The Letter is unclear on which version of the caliphate it promotes. After the first centuries of Islam, the theories on the caliphate increasingly allowed a separation of spiritual and political leadership due to the existence of multiple rulers in the *Dar al-Islam*. In a sense, three main approaches developed over the centuries: 1) The caliphate encompasses both political and religious leadership (*imama*, i.e. being a supreme *Faqih*, judge, military and political ruler), 2) the caliphate (or sultan) has been reduced to pure political leadership (*imamat al-Dawla* or *sultaniyya* i.e. military and political ruler, and occasional judge) whereby the scholars have become the heirs of the Prophet in religious leadership (*imamat al-Din*, as *Fuqaha* and judges), 3) the caliphate is purely religious (i.e. supreme jurist) while the Muslim lands are politically ruled by one or more rulers (i.e. military and political rulers). There is no doubt that approach 1 represented the caliphate after the Prophet when it was ruled by his companions (*Sahaba*) and their successors (*Tabi'in*) who are seen as sources of Islamic law (some in personal opinion as Abu Bakr, Umar, Uthman, Ali and Ibn Umar, the others are generally taken in under consensus). After these two generations (when the Abbasid took over in 750 CE) approaches 2-3 developed as pragmatical models to deal with the

political reality of their times, but more importantly, to keep the ruler subject to the law and thereby restraining his possible oppressive behaviour. The Letter claims the caliphate is an obligation, but technically classical Islam saw political rule (*imama*) as an obligation as a means for several ends: 1) To defend society against military enemies, 2) to restrain oppression and provide good state administration, 3) to enforce the rule of law through courts and represent those without caretakers or guardians (e.g. orphans, widows, insane), 4) to divide the revenues and spent it for the welfare of society, 5) to ensure the safe performance of prayer and pilgrimage, 6) to represent the unity of the global Muslim community. A ruler is technically just a mediator (*Wakil*) for the different social groups and classes, and ensures its general welfare (*masalih al-'Amm*). Islam doesn't see itself as a political religion, but first of all as a civilizational religion. Following Greek philosophy, wherein man is portrayed as a social animal who needs rulers to ward off general violence and oppression, classical Islamic thought directly linked civilization to be in need of a political and military structure to provide an order of law and economy. This is also the reason why political rule (*imama*) is mainly discussed in creedal works ('*aqida* and '*ilm al-Kalam*) instead of the works of law; Sunni Islam disagreed with the theological grounds of the political concepts of other groups such as the demand for a divinely protected leader (Shi'ite), or a moral and religious puritan as leader (Kharijite), or that political rule was purely a rational need (Mu'tazilite). The civilizational need for a political order can be discerned by reason, but the religious obligation of such an order was understood to be commanded by God Himself in Qur'an 4:59. The early caliphs were seen as the perfect mix between philosopher-kings and *Fuquha* (approach 1), but their successors (approaches 2) were generally expected to be just philosopher-kings who maintained government administration and the order of law in cooperation with the *Fuquha*. A ruler also has no 'divine right of kings', as he is only a means to fulfill the divine and human rights pursued by the Shari'a. This is also why governance in classical Islam does not conform to general conceptions of theocracy, as the religion is a bottom-up construction (i.e. the religion of the people representing the will of the people) in which scholars pursue general welfare of the people. Not all Sunni jurists saw the caliphate as an obligation, or belonging to the Qurayshi lineage (interestingly enough these two opinions were also upheld by Ibn Taymiyya), but they all saw governance as a necessity. And governance needs rulers, whether you call them caliphs, sultans, kings or emirs. With the decline of Abbasid power in the 10th century, whereby their political and military rule was usurped by others, the caliphate was turned into a mere religious symbolic role (approach 3), until the title was transferred to the Ottomans in 1517 (thereby combining caliphate and sultanate again). When the power of the Ottomans waned and many Muslim lands were colonized by Europe in the late 19th century, the concept of Pan-Islamism (which also falls under approach 3) was introduced to promote the caliphatal leadership of the Ottoman sultan over the global Muslim population (see fn. 13 above). After the abolishment of the Ottoman caliphate, reformist thinkers as Muhammad Rashid Rida (d. 1935) theorized the caliphate purely from a Pan-Islamist perspective (approach 3), as a symbol for Muslim unity. A caliph could be elected by the local Muslim community or their elective council (*Shura*) when they lived in one of the central cities or regions of the Muslim lands (as was the case with the election of Abu Bakr and 'Umar), as the election by the whole Muslim *Umma* was deemed impossible. Later Sunni theorists allowed three ways a caliph could come into power: 1) Designation by the previous ruler as a form of testament (*Wasiyya*), 2) election (*ikhtiyariyya*) by community (*Umma*) or elective council (*Shura* or *Ahl al-Hall wa al-'Aqd*) as a form of consensus, 3) or by force (*qahriyya*). When a person is designated or has taken power through force, he stills needs to be acknowledged by the *Umma* and the main scholars to acknowledge his rulership through consensus by way of swearing allegiance (*bay'a*). Technically there could only be one caliph at one time, due to the fact that he ruled the whole of the Muslim *Umma* and represented their unity, but historically there were many rulers claiming the caliphate at the same time. What is allowed is multiple political rulers ruling over separate lands with or without an acknowledged caliph as a spiritual authority (approach 2-3). If we look at ISIS' election of al-Baghdadi, the Letter is correct to state that an election by such a small group, without any consultation with larger representative councils, cannot claim to have established a caliphate over 1.6 billion Muslims. Also their claim that their caliphate is in the way of the first generations (approach 1) would mean that al-Baghdadi can claim absolute *ijtihad* and is not subject to the consensus of that generation. Although their Salafi-Wahhabism does renounce to be bound (*taqlid*) to the opinions and consensus of the Sunni schools, they do claim to be

23. Loyalty to one's nation is permissible in Islam.¹¹⁶

bound to the first generations of Muslims (see fn. 96 above). Therefore they can only claim an approach 2-3 caliphate, which separated worldly and religious authority, and which is bound to the opinions of the schools and the majority of Muslims. And in this way they would indeed be subject to the requirements the Letter provides: an acceptance by a consensus or at least a majority of Muslim governments and scholarly organizations. ISIS rejects democracy, and especially multiparty democracy, as a form of *Kufr* (see fn. 90 above. This is also the reason why Jihadi-Salafism declared the Muslim Brotherhood as heretics), while modern Sunnism has accepted democratic rule as a form of *Sultaniyya* (approach 2). It is doubtful any caliph apart from approach 3 will be accepted by the majority of Muslims, nor a return to a pre-democratic state, as global statistics among the global Muslim community show a clear support and adherence to democratic politics, whereby the Shari'a is mainly understood as representing a value-system (e.g. justice, peace, freedom, anti-corruption) instead of simply a form of law. If the caliphate, or general Islamic politics, can be democratic can be answered with a simple yes. The Tanzimat already made the caliphate into a constitutional monarchy, almost all Muslim monarchies today have followed that model, and the majority of Muslim countries are constitutional democracies. Apart from the current prevalent despotism, it can not be denied that modern Islam has become democratic in theory and practice. Lambton, *Ibid*, 55-58, 70-95, 105-129, 132-137, 140-151, 165-166. El-Awa, *Ibid*, 75-82. Arnold, *Ibid*, 42-54, 70-76, 107-128, 173-181. Asma Afsaruddin, ed., *Islam, the State, and Political Authority: Medieval Issues and Modern Concerns* (New York: Palgrave Macmillan, 2011), 9-34, 111-129. Sherman A. Jackson, *Islamic Law and the State: The Constitutional Jurisprudence of Shihab Al-Din Al-Qarafi* (Leiden: Brill, 1996), 185 – 224. Akgündüz, *Ibid*, 55-60, 151-184. 'Abd Allāh al-Baydawi, *Tawāl'i al-Anwār min Matāl'i al-Anzār* (Cairo: Maktabah al-Azhariyyah li-Turāth, n.d.), 235–47. Al-Juwayni, *Ibid*. Al-Dabusi, *Ibid*, 417. Al-Mawardi, *Ibid*, 10–34, 45-56. Belkeziz, *Ibid*, 119-218. Khaled Abou El Fadl e.a., *Islam and the challenge of democracy: A "Boston review" book* (United States: Princeton University press, 2004). Khaled Abou El Fadl, "Constitutionalism and the Islamic Sunni Legacy", *UCLA J. Islamic & Near E. L.* 1, no. 67 (2001). Darling, *Ibid*, 191-208. Akhtar, *Ibid*, 174-183. Black, *Ibid*, 9-31, 57-114, 154-159, 165-182, 197-220, 239-348. Amjad M. Mohammed, *Muslims in Non-Muslim lands: A legal study with applications* (United Kingdom: The Islamic Texts Society, 2013), 125–28. For discussions on Muslim approaches to democratic constitutionalism, see: Rainer Grote and Tilmann J. Roder, *Constitutionalism in Islamic Countries: Between Upheaval and Continuity* (New York: Oxford University Press, USA, 2012). Jeremy Kleidosty, *The concert of civilizations: The common roots of western and Islamic Constitutionalism* (United Kingdom: Ashgate Publishing, 2015). *Most Muslims want democracy, personal freedoms, and Islam in political life*, (n.p.: Pew Research Center's Global Attitudes Project, 2012), <http://www.pewglobal.org/2012/07/10/most-muslims-want-democracy-personal-freedoms-and-islam-in-political-life/>.

¹¹⁶ Letter, *Ibid*, 24. Here the Letter attacks ISIS' usurpation of land of native Iraqi's and Syrians, and compares this usurpation and call for foreigners to emigrate to it as similar to the way Israel has claimed Palestine. This ingenious accusation uses the Muslim sensibility for the plight of Palestine, and also creates awareness to the fact that an emigration towards ISIS held territory would imply the takeover of other Muslims' property and resources. Secondly the Letter responds to the question of nationality, which Islamism has generally viewed as a form of tribalism (*asabiyya*) which runs counter to Muslim unity, and which ISIS' Jihadi-Salafism declares as *Kufr* in the same as it does multiparty democracy. The Letter provides two proofs for their acceptance of nationalism, of which the statement of Ibn Hajar al-Asqalani (d. 1449) carries the most weight due to him being the most important commentator on the Hadith collection of Bukhari. Nationalism raises two issues which are not discussed: Muslim majority (*Dar al-Islam*) nationalism and Muslim minority (*Dar al-Kufr*) nationalism. The former is mainly approached from Pan-Islamism: why can't Muslim majority countries be united both in religion and political rule? The failure to unite is generally seen as also a failure in being truly faithful to Islam. This anti-nationalism responded to the break up of the Ottoman empire and the way European powers used Muslim nationalism for Western interests. Historically, Muslim majority countries have always been divided in

24. After the death of the Prophet, Islam does not require anyone to emigrate anywhere.¹¹⁷

multiple empires, kingdoms, and provinces. The idea of the Muslim *Umma* has always created a supra-nationalist identity, but has never been a replacement of ethnic and cultural identities among that *Umma*, and was never meant to do so. The latter issue concerns Muslim minorities in non-Muslim countries: Can they, as immigrants or natives, be nationalistic of their non-Muslim nation, which technically is *Dar al-Kufr*? The issue here revolves around the legal possibility of adherence and/or compliance to non-Muslim governance and law, and how this relates to the concept of *Ummaic* allegiance and disassociation of unbelievers (*al-Wala wa al-Bara*), which was central to Kharijite thought (and still is in the existing Kharijite offshoot of Ibadi theology) and is central to Salafi-Wahhabism. How can one be a Muslim who is loyal to his faith and global community, and also be loyal to a society that does not adhere to this faith, maybe allow laws abhorred by or restrict the application of Islam, and possibly fight against Muslim majority countries? This has been an issue since Muslims ventured into non-Muslim lands as warriors, traders, or residents. If Muslims lived in non-Muslims lands which have treaties with Muslim majority countries (as is the case for the majority of countries), then such countries are *Dar al-Sulh* (abode of peace treaty) and not *Dar al-Harb*. According to Hanafi scholars, if such countries also allowed Muslims to worship and live freely, then they can be regarded as *Dar al-Islam*. Also with the prevalence and overlap of international and national law between the majority of countries in the world, can most countries provide citizenship and freedom of worship to Muslims. This citizenship requires minimal loyalty and adherence to local law and taxes, and most western countries have no military draft, so the chance of fighting fellow Muslims is minimal. As for any laws that are allowed by these countries, but are abhorred by Islamic law (such as gay marriage), can be approached the same way abhorred practices of the *Ahl al-Dhimma* were allowed within the *Dar al-Islam* (such as brother-sister marriages among the Zoroastrians). The question of *al-Wala wa al-Bara* therefore does not apply on the level of citizenship of non-Muslim countries (i.e. having a nationality). This is also how Qur'an 8:72 was understood: people are not obligated to migrate, and if they are oppressed and ask for help, Muslims cannot attack that land if it is in treaty with the *Dar al-Islam*. Amjad Mohammed, *Ibid*, 129-147. Bin Ali, *Ibid*, 66-80, 121-150, 159-183. Valerie J Hoffman, *The essentials of Ibadi Islam* (Syracuse, NY: Syracuse University Press, 2012), 156–230. Said Fares Hassan, *Fiqh Al-Aqalliyat: History, development, and progress* (United Kingdom: Palgrave Macmillan, 2013), 27, 116-117, 148-152. Andrew F March, *Islamic and liberal citizenship the search for an overlapping consensus* (New York: Oxford University Press, 2009), 111–27, 140-151, 181-206, 237-258. Maurits S Berger, *A brief history of Islam in Europe: Thirteen centuries of creed, conflict and coexistence* (United States: Amsterdam University Pr, 2015), 74–84, 199-210. Khadduri, *Islamic Law of Nations*, 130-141. Al-Dawoody, *Ibid*, 92-102. Al-Yaqoubi, *Ibid*, 28-30. Nasr, *The Study Quran*, 500-501. Jonathan Brown, “The Shariah, Homosexuality & Safeguarding Each Other’s Rights in a Pluralist Society”, *Al-Madina Institute* June 18, 2016, accessed August 6, 2016, <http://almadinainstitute.org/blog/the-shariah-homosexuality-safeguarding-each-others-rights-in-a-pluralist-so/>.

¹¹⁷ Letter, *Ibid*, 24-25. The question of emigration towards ISIS territory is connected to their claim of being the only true *Dar al-Islam*, which is nonsensical as stated above at fn. 115. Even if ISIS’ claim to the caliphate would be accepted, they cannot claim to be the only *Dar al-Islam*. Emigration is only obligated for those who cannot worship openly, and they only need to emigrate towards a country where they can worship freely. And for those who can already worship freely, emigration is not necessary. As for emigration to support other Muslims who are attacked, it only becomes a personal obligation (*fard kifaya*) when non-Muslims invade Muslim lands and defensive warfare (*jihad al-Dafa*) is required. And this is not the case with the Arab Spring in Syria. Only after the rise of ISIS did an international coalition form against it, which is a coalition of Muslim and non-Muslim countries who are bound by international treaties. Amjad Mohammed, *Ibid*, 145-147. Al-Dawoody, *Ibid*, 76. Al-Yaqoubi, *Ibid*, 28-30.

Individual anti-ISIS Fatwa's

Three of the signatory scholars have also written individual fatwa's against ISIS. Shaykh Muhammad al-Yaqoubi, a Syrian mufti who fled to America after denouncing both the Syrian regime and the Jihadist groups (although he does support the Free Syrian Army)¹¹⁸, addresses the general Muslim community and non-Muslim allies against ISIS, whereby he focuses on how the acts of ISIS (i.e. their atrocities and their general excommunication of other Muslims) prove they are Kharijite. By making ISIS fall within the Kharijite category, al-Yaqoubi can apply classical rulings which made fighting Kharijite groups an obligation, thereby turning the obligation of Jihad on ISIS itself.¹¹⁹ He also sees the western and Arab alliance against ISIS as permissible as ISIS is the greatest threat to Muslims, Islam, Middle Eastern societies, and the world. On this last issue he responds to a general tactic used by extremists to gain sympathy from the general Muslim masses whereby they present the western-Arab alliance and Muslims living in the West, or even those that have joined western armies, as traitors who cooperate with non-Muslims in fighting other Muslims.¹²⁰

Shaykh Abdallah Bin Bayyah, a Mauritian scholar famous for his fatwa's on issues pertaining to Muslim minorities¹²¹, addresses in his fatwa "the young men who bear arms against their own nations and destroy both country and countrymen." In it he discusses nine

¹¹⁸ Tam Hussein, *The revolt of the Sheikh*.

¹¹⁹ As Tahir-ul-Qadri has also done in his 2010 fatwa. Tahir-ul-Qadri, *Ibid*, 331-334.

¹²⁰ Shaykh Muhammad al-Yaqoubi, *Refuting ISIS: A Rebuttal of its Religious and Ideological Foundations*, 1st ed. (United Kingdom: Sacred Knowledge, 2015). A second edition has come out which has been expanded with 140 more pages, but I haven't been able to review it for this paper.

¹²¹ Souheila Al-Jadda and Amina Chaudary, *Why America needs to know this man*, (The Islamic Monthly), march 4, 2014, <http://theislamicmonthly.com/why-america-needs-to-know-this-man/>.

points that summarize his views of Sharia principles, righteous Jihad, and the requirements of legitimacy for a Caliphate. He argues that the Sharia serves one general principle: the preserving of life. So resistance against oppressive government (i.e. Syrian regime) is justified, but the methods used by ISIS and other Jihadist groups are wrong as they clearly violate this principle. He also argues that their implementation of Sharia penal laws violate classical stipulations which strictly restricted the application of penal punishments to occasions when they can serve as a means of deterrence and not as the general ruling for all such crimes. He further argues that Jihad is only legitimate in a defensive struggle between states, and only to pursue justice and peace. It is not meant for rebellion, conquest, causing chaos and fear or continued hostility. There is no obligation to establish a Caliphate through warfare, it can only be established through general Muslim consensus. Non-Muslim minorities living in Muslim lands are to be protected and never persecuted or coerced into Islam. The majority of the classical schools accepted all non-Muslim groups as deserving protection, to claim only some minorities deserve protection is to deliberately seek out opinions that do not generate the largest welfare and justice for mankind. He warns that Sharia is based on wisdom, justice, mercy and the common good and that actions that ignore these or create an image of Islam that is the opposite of these can not be claimed to be in the defense of Islam as they drive people away from Islam and turn people against the Muslim community.¹²²

Dr. Shawki Allam, the Grand Mufti of Egypt and head of al-Azhar university¹²³, has collected several articles and fatwa's into a book to address the problems around ISIS. Al-

¹²² Shaykh Abdallah Bin Bayyah, "Fatwa Response to ISIS: This is Not the Path to Paradise" (2014), accessed 7-12-2015, www.binbayyah.net/english/2014/09/24/fatwa-response-to-isis/.

¹²³ On the history and significance of al-Azhar, see: Bayard Dodge, *Al-Azhar: A Millenium of Muslim Learning* (United States of America : The American International Printing Company , 1961).

Azhar had started a campaign wherein it asked global media and leaders to not use the term “Islamic State” but rather QGIS, short for al-Qaeda separatists in Iraq and Syria, as using Islamic state would affect Muslims living in the West and increase global Islamophobia. The book contains several fatwa’s on Jihad; how to interpret the Qur’an verses on fighting; the application of the penal laws; war ethics in Islam; ISIS and other terrorists being the contemporary Kharijite; how extremists misunderstand Islam; that Islam pursues a religious pluralistic society; how to deal with sons who want to go on Jihad; slavery; and the unlawfulness of raping captives.¹²⁴

Conclusion

One of the interesting aspects of these counter responses against extremism is that they show how mainstream Sunni Islam, partially as a response to extremism, has incorporated modernist and reformist thought on reinterpretation of the Qur’an and the Islamic tradition, and on human rights, liberal governance, and religious pluralism.¹²⁵ They discuss the same subjects and provide similar interpretations and sources, thereby generating a general consensus among the contemporary Sunni orthodoxy on Jihad and the modern state (i.e. democracy, secular law and equal citizenship). These counter responses not only involve the discussion on ‘what is classical Islam’ and Islam and modern democracy, but also on Muslim minorities in non-Muslim countries. The fact that these counter responses are released simultaneously in Arabic and English show both the effect of globalism on normative Islamic discourse (to be internationally known, one has to publish in English), and

¹²⁴ Grand Mufti Shawki Allam and Al-Azhar university's Dar al-ifta (House of Fatwa’s), *The Ideological Battlefield: Egypt’s Dar al-ifta Combats Radicalization* (2014), accessed 7-12-2015, www.eng.dar-alifta.org/OnlineBooks/The%20Ideological%20Battle.pdf.

¹²⁵ Ruthven, *Ibid*, 323-324.

that English is the second most important language to educate non-Arabic speaking Muslims and counter Islamophobia among non-Arabic speaking non-Muslims. This can also be seen with other Islamic declarations, such as the Marrakesh declaration (January 2016) which was formulated in Arabic but also directly came with an English summary.¹²⁶ Islamic terrorism and radicalism has forced scholars representing mainstream Islam to openly and clearly declare their positions on pluralism, democracy and human rights. The demand for clarity has helped (or forced?) mainstream Sunni scholars to formulate positions beyond mere apologetics. The subject of slavery was normally addressed by declaring it apologetically and falsely as ‘unIslamic’¹²⁷, or by declaring it as obsolete or impossible to practice today. With the Letter’s clear declaration that slavery was abolished both by Muslim community consensus (*ijma’ al-Umma*) and by worldly consensus (*ijma’ al-‘alam*), it has made multifaith/secular globalistic consensus a source for the Shari’a.¹²⁸ The difference in density of Islamic totalism, using Shepard’s typology¹²⁹, between radical Islamists as ISIS and the mainstream Sunni Islam constructed by the Letter differs immensely due to the latter’s acceptance of equalizing (and even superseding of) the Shari’a with international and civil law in matters of religious pluralism (by historicizing the Jizya), warfare, and nationalism. The globalization of Islamic radicalism has forced mainstream Sunni Islam to globalize not only its discourse, but also its content.

¹²⁶ “Marrakesh declaration”, 2016, accessed juli 7, 2016, <http://marrakeshdeclaration.org/>. The Marrakesh Declaration is also an important development as it calls for a harmonization between the Shari’a and the UNDHR, whereby it ignores the OIC adhered to Islamist human rights construction of the Cairo Declaration of Human Rights.

¹²⁷ The vast majority of Muslims reject the concept of slavery, showing the success of post-Enlightenment humanism in the Muslim world.

¹²⁸ As can also be seen with the Marrakesh Declaration promotion of the United Nations Declaration of Human Rights (UNDHR) as criteria for Shari’a interpretations.

¹²⁹ William E. Shepard, “Islam and ideology: Towards a typology”, 317-326.

Appendix I: Comparison between ‘Letter to Baghdadi’ and RISSC designs

Executive Summary

- 1- It is forbidden in Islam to issue *fatwas* without all the necessary learning requirements. Even then *fatwas* must follow Islamic legal theory as defined in the Classical texts. It is also forbidden to cite a portion of a verse from the Qur'an—or part of a verse—to derive a ruling without looking at everything that the Qur'an and *Hadith* teach related to that matter. In other words, there are strict subjective and objective prerequisites for *fatwas*, and one cannot 'cherry-pick' Qur'anic verses for legal arguments without considering the entire Qur'an and *Hadith*.
- 2- It is forbidden in Islam to issue legal rulings about anything without mastery of the Arabic language.

Figure 2. Original website

Figure 3. Redesigned website

Figure 4. Redesigned PDF 'Letter to Baghdadi'

Figure 5. RISSC publication designs

Appendix II: Timeline of Islamism and Radicalism (figure 6)

Appendix III: Anti-Letter meme

Figure 7: Anti-Letter meme found on the internet, it is unclear if this meme was created by ISIS supporters or by Islamophobes who reject the Letter's claim on normative Islam.

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